

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Deliverable D5.1.(D09) Concept for model interactions and baseline, and mapping research topics to modelling tools

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ACRONYMS

AGMEMOD	AGricultural MEmber State MODelling
AGMIP	AGricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project
BAU	Business-as-usual
CAP	Common agricultural policy
CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact model
CH4	Methane
CO2	Carbon dioxide
DG	Directorate General
EC	European Commission
EPIC	Environmental Policy Integrated Climate Model
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
GLOBIOM	Global Biosphere Management Model
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis Project
G4M	Global Forest Model
IAM	Integrated Assessment Model
IAMC	Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium
ILR	Insitute for Food and Ressource Economics, University of Bonn
IMAGE	Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment
IMAP	Agroeconomic Commodity and Policy Analysis
K	Kalium
MAGNET	Modular Agricultural GeNeral Equilibrium Tool
MS	Member State
N	Nitrogen
N2O	Nitrous Oxide
JRC	Join Research Centre
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
P	Phosphorous
PE	Partial Equilibrium
RCP	Reference Concentration Pathway
SJOS	Safe and Just Operating Space

SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathway
WP	Work package
WR	Wageningen Research
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To create a robust toolbox for analysing the transition towards a Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS) for the EU agriculture system, in Work Package (WP) 5 we first focus on model assessment, integration, and stakeholder engagement. Technical and methodological advancements of existing models are pursued in dedicated Work Packages but here we organise their coordinated use in a toolbox. A dedicated workshop facilitated the initial mapping of the model outputs to the SJOS thematic areas and indicator domains. Causal loop diagramming was used to clarify the relationships between SJOS variables, guiding our selection of suitable models and identifying potential overlaps, gaps, and semantic differences.

We also created a first version of the BrightSpace baseline with a focus on the medium-run business as usual development and prepared the next steps which are the key uncertainties with some likelihood to determine the future. Preliminary ideas have been developed and will be presented to stakeholders in the first stakeholder retreat to discuss and possibly pick up determinants that have been so far neglected or ranked less important by the consortium.

1. INTRODUCTION

BrightSpace Pillar 2 focuses on developing a modelling framework to quantify and project future pathways within the Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS). Our approach emphasises integration across geographic scales, connecting socio-economic and biophysical models to address the wide scope of relevant EU policies. Our integrated model toolbox combines EU-wide, global, regional, and farm/household models, offering comprehensive SJOS indicators (food security, employment, biodiversity, etc.). This multi-level approach allows us to examine both the direct effects on decision-making units and the indirect effects of EU policies and global events. Key models in our toolbox include IMAGE, GLOBIOM, MAGNET at the global level; AGMEMOD, CAPRI at the EU/Member State level; FarmDyn and simFNS at the farm/household level; and MITERRA-EUROPE at the grid level. This stylised mapping of modelling systems and levels neglects that some systems cover several levels. Also, in terms of topics, these models are partly complementary but also overlapping. IMAGE, GLOBIOM, and MITERRA have detailed bio-physical representations and many applications on greenhouse gases (GHG), soil carbon and biodiversity impacts. MAGNET, AGMEMOD, FarmDyn, and simFNS are focused more on economic effects, with CAPRI as an intermediate case. Hence, we consider various forms of interplay of these models:

- Models may be applied in a complementary manner to achieve a full coverage of relevant topics.
- They may be applied in a supplementary way providing insights on the uncertainties from using different methodologies or parameterisations.
- Models may be partly integrated in two ways: bottom-up improvement of tools used by the EC and top-down downscaling of macro model results.

WP5 will also map out SJOS pathways by co-creating a BrightSpace baseline with stakeholders. We'll present key baseline drivers linked to SJOS indicators to stakeholders and collect their input into model-ready indicators. The BrightSpace baseline and alternative futures will inform future scenario analysis and model development across the project.

The main objectives in this report are to show the progress towards:

- The BrightSpace modelling framework for modelling SJOS indicators selected in Pillar 1 (see D1.1).
- The BrightSpace baseline scenario

This report offers a structured analysis of the Brightspace modelling toolbox and its application to SJOS indicator modelling. Below is a breakdown of its key sections:

- **Section 1: Model Overview and Workshop Results**
 - Introduces each model within the BrightSpace toolbox.
 - Summarises the outcomes of the initial Brightspace modelling workshop, which focused on developing a conceptual framework for modelling SJOS indicators. This involved:
 - Identifying which BrightSpace SJOS indicator domains each model covers.
 - Outlining the underlying processes (demand, supply, policy) influencing these indicators and how each model simulates them.
- **Section 2: BrightSpace Baseline Development**

- Delves into the process of establishing the BrightSpace baseline, a critical reference point for modelling and analysis.
- **Section 3: Next Steps and Conclusion**
 - Outlines the planned progression of the modelling work.
 - Presents conclusions drawn from the modelling efforts thus far.

2. BRIGHTSPACE SJOS MODELLING FRAMEWORK

This section provides a brief overview of each model within the BrightSpace toolbox. It also summarises the results of working sessions that explored modelling BrightSpace SJOS indicators using the toolbox. For each model, the section outlines the specific BrightSpace SJOS indicators addressed, the underlying demand, supply, and policy processes relevant to those indicators, and the approach taken to model them. A detailed description of each model, including a comprehensive list of model indicators, can be found in Annex 1.

2.1. MAGNET

The Modular Agricultural GeNeral Equilibrium Tool (MAGNET) is a flexible economic model based on the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP). It analyses production, trade, and factor use across various sectors and regions, using extensive input-output and trade data. MAGNET's modular design allows users to customise it for specific studies. It includes features like land heterogeneity analysis, agricultural policy representation (including the EU's Common Agricultural Policy – CAP), and biofuel modelling. This model can simulate scenarios that include changes in trade, technology, policy, and environmental indicators, enabling the analysis of their economic and environmental effects (Woltjer et al., 2014).

MAGNET analyses the economy-wide and distributional impacts of policy and/or structural shocks, sectoral transmission of sector-specific policies for sectors, agents and regions. The output of MAGNET includes projections of input-output tables, GDP, employment, bilateral trade, capital flows and household consumption. The explicit formulation of representative households allows the derivation of welfare indicators. Annex 1 features a tabular presentation of MAGNET output indicators, offering a detailed breakdown.

The model is designed for policy simulations. First, it establishes a reference scenario (or baseline) over a future time period. This baseline incorporates existing conditions and assumptions. Next, the model creates a new scenario by modifying one or more underlying assumptions (including policies, taxes, or tariffs). This new scenario is simulated over the same time period. By comparing the results of the new scenario to the baseline, the model reveals the impacts of the simulated changes in terms of percentage differences across all relevant variables.

MAGNET uses baseline scenarios to establish a reference point for comparing the effects of changes in policies or other factors. The model's baseline scenario for the BrightSpace project spans from 2017 up to at least 2050 and incorporates historical and projected data for GDP, agricultural productivity, and other key factors. This scenario helps illustrate how current economic and environmental trends could evolve in a "business-as-usual" context. MAGNET's results present changes in value, price, quantity, production, trade, resource use, emissions, and employment. It also incorporates tools like GEMPACK decomposition, which helps isolate the relative importance of policy changes and other factors in shaping outcomes. For a detailed description of MAGNET please see Annex 1.

Visually explaining the MAGNET model's coverage of BrightSpace SJOS indicator domains and the underlying processes for deriving them, Figure 1 is the result of the BrightSpace modelling workshop.

Figure 1: BrightSpace SJOS indicator modelling in MAGNET: coverage and modelling process

2.2. GLOBIOM

The Global Biosphere Management Model (GLOBIOM) is a partial equilibrium (PE) model designed to simulate interactions between the agriculture, forestry, and bioenergy sectors (IBF-IIASA, 2023). The supply-side of the model is built from the bottom (spatially explicit land cover, land use, management systems and economic cost information) to the top (regional commodity markets). Demand is determined at the level of aggregate regions. Food demand projections are based on the interaction of three different drivers: population growth, per-capita income growth, and response to prices (based on consumer preferences), and policies. The spatial resolution of the supply side relies on the concept of Simulation Units that are aggregates of 5 to 30 arcmin pixels belonging to the same altitude, slope, and soil class, and following country borders. For crops, livestock, and forest products, spatially explicit Leontief production functions covering alternative production systems are parameterised using biophysical models like Environmental Policy Integrated Climate Model (EPIC) or Global Forest Model (G4M). GLOBIOM covers major GHG emissions from Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) based on IPCC accounting guidelines. These include nitrous oxide (N₂O) from application of synthetic fertiliser and manure to soils, N₂O from manure dropped on pastures, CH₄ from rice cultivation, N₂O and methane (CH₄) from manure management, and CH₄ from enteric fermentation, and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions/removals from above- and below-ground biomass changes for other natural vegetation following conversion. CO₂ emissions/removals from afforestation, deforestation, wood production in managed forests are estimated by the geographically explicit (0.5x0.5 degree) model G4M that is connected to GLOBIOM based on the parameters derived from G4M (Kindermann et al., 2006). Figure 2 depicts the interconnected elements and relationships within the GLOBIOM modelling framework.

Figure 2: GLOBIOM modelling framework

For some select cases, GLOBIOM also provides input into G4M (Gusti et al., 2008) which is used to calculate forest emissions. In addition, GLOBIOM endogenously represents GHG mitigation technologies including technological and structural mitigation options.

Commodity markets and international trade are modelled at the level of aggregate economic regions (the aggregation is flexible and can be adapted to the users' needs) where prices are endogenously determined at the regional level to establish market equilibrium. Trade is modelled following the spatial equilibrium approach representing bilateral trade flows based on cost competitiveness and homogeneous good assumption. Besides primary products for the different sectors, the model has several final and by-products, for which, processing activities are defined. The model computes market equilibrium for agricultural and forest products by allocating land use among production activities to maximise the sum of producer and consumer surplus, subject to resource, technological, demand and policy constraints. GLOBIOM captures the multiple interrelationships between different systems involved in production of agricultural and forestry products. For example, population dynamics, changes in socio-economic and technological conditions, ecosystems and climate that lead to adjustments in the product mix and the use of land and other productive resources. The model is calibrated to an average around the year 2000 and solved recursively dynamic, typically done in 10-year time steps, and depending on the study, going up to 2100.

GLOBIOM's baseline scenario models "business as usual" to provide a reference for comparison. It uses historical data, Reference Concentration Pathway (RCP), and Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP2) scenarios to project demand, supply, land use change, trade, and other indicators up to 2100.

Typically, the model results are reported in the AgMIP or IAMC template which covers, amongst other, information on:

- Market balances and activity levels: production, areas, yields, food-, feed-, other consumption, bilateral trade flows etc.
- Socio-economic indicators: such as product prices, food consumption, undernourishment etc.
- Environmental indicators: land use and land use changes, deforestation, GHG emissions, fertiliser and irrigation water use, biodiversity impacts etc.

Annex 1 provides a detailed description of the GLOBIOM model.

Figure 3, a key outcome of the BrightSpace modelling workshop, provides a visual explanation of the GLOBIOM model's coverage of BrightSpace SJOS indicator domains and the underlying modelling processes.

Figure 3. GLOBIOM SJOS indicator modelling in MAGNET: coverage and modelling process

2.3. AGMEMOD

AGMEMOD is an econometric, dynamic, partial-equilibrium model designed to analyse the main EU agri-food markets at the member state level. It utilises statistical analysis of historical data to project future trends and simulate the impacts of policy changes, macroeconomic shifts, or other market disruptions. AGMEMOD covers a wide range of agricultural commodities across all EU member states, including specialised crops that aren't typically represented in broader aggregate models. Additionally, the BioMAT module delivers insights into markets for bio-based products, highlighting potential trade-offs and competition between food, feed, and material uses for agricultural biomass. The AGMEMOD model is an integral part of the Integrated Modelling Platform for Agro-economic Commodity and Policy Analysis (iMAP) hosted by the JRC (M'barek et al., 2012; M'barek and Delincé, 2015).

AGMEMOD's structure emphasises the interconnectedness of agricultural sectors. Models for crops, livestock, and dairy are linked, capturing interactions such as crop land allocation decisions, the derived demand for feedstuffs, and substitutions within consumer diets. Behavioural equations underpin the model, simulating how economic actors (farmers, consumers, etc.) respond to price changes, policy shifts, and other variables. Prices are determined through transmission equations, linking domestic markets to international markets and considering key factors like EU self-sufficiency rates and world prices. The model incorporates recursive dynamics, meaning decisions in the current period have consequences that reverberate into future periods.

AGMEMOD is used to generate both medium-term baseline projections for EU and member-state agricultural markets and for policy scenario analysis. It simulates the effects of potential policy changes, allowing policymakers to assess the likely impacts of different interventions at the EU or member-state level. The annual baseline outlook is developed in close collaboration with the European Commission to ensure alignment with current policy assumptions. This process leverages macroeconomic assumptions, detailed EU policy information, and feedback gathered from national agricultural experts. Key output indicators generated by AGMEMOD include:

- Production volumes (by commodity and country)
- Land use (crop categories and country)
- Yields (per hectare, crop, country)
- Livestock numbers (by species and country)
- Domestic use (by commodity and country)
- Biomass allocation (food, feed, seed, material uses)
- Net trade (by commodity and country)
- Commodity prices (Euros/kg)
- Greenhouse gas emissions (livestock, by country)
- Plant/animal protein intake (grams, per person, country)

For a detailed description of the AGMEMOD model, refer to Annex 1.

Figure 4 (a key outcome of the BrightSpace modelling workshop) visually illustrates how the AGMEMOD model addresses BrightSpace SJOS indicator domains and their modelling processes.

Figure 4.: Brightspace SJOS indicator modelling in AGMEMOD: coverage and modelling process

2.4. CAPRI

The Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact (CAPRI) model is a powerful tool for assessing the impact of agricultural, environmental, and trade policies on the European Union's agricultural sector and beyond (Britz and Witzke, 2014). Its global coverage, detailed databases, and modular structure make it adaptable to various analyses.

The CAPRI model uses well-documented official data sources (EUROSTAT, FAOSTAT, OECD, FADN) to ensure accuracy and consistency (Britz and Witzke, 2014). Its economic modelling philosophy prioritises structural consistency across products, regions, and activities for enhanced comparability and ease of integration (Britz and Witzke, 2014).

CAPRI is built for scenario analysis using a comparative static approach, interpreting results as long-term outcomes (Britz and Witzke, 2014). To establish a reference point, CAPRI simulations begin with a baseline scenario that integrates projections from external sources like the DG-AGRI Agricultural Outlook (European Commission, 2023).

The model has two interacting modules: supply and market (Figure 1). The supply module uses regional non-linear programming models to optimise agricultural income at the regional or farm-type level (Britz and Witzke, 2014; Jansson and Heckelei, 2011). It provides detailed modelling of agricultural inputs, activities, and policy measures. The market module, a global multi-commodity model, calculates equilibrium through iterations with the supply module (Britz and Witzke, 2014). It models supply, demand, trade, and related policy instruments for agricultural products, delivering price information to the supply module and allowing for global, EU, and national market analysis.

CAPRI includes environmental indicators, primarily for nutrient surpluses (N, P, K) and greenhouse gas emissions (Britz and Witzke, 2014). Nutrient balances and IPCC methodology provide the basis for these calculations. The model's flexibility allows users to run specific modules independently for focused analysis.

Post-model analysis covers income indicators, welfare analysis, detailed modelling of CAP outlays, and the option for spatial downscaling of results (Britz and Witzke, 2014). The CAPRI baseline combines a historical CAPRI database with external projections, ensuring consistency and alignment with established outlooks (Britz and Witzke, 2014; European Commission, 2023).

Main CAPRI Outputs

- **Economic:** Production, activity levels, feed/fodder use, trade, income, CAP budget, prices (Britz and Witzke, 2014).
- **Environmental:** GHG emissions, NPK balances, energy/water use, biodiversity indicators (Britz and Witzke, 2014).

Annex 1 provides a comprehensive explanation of the CAPRI model. To see how it addresses BrightSpace SJOS indicator domains and their modelling processes, check out Figure 5 (a key outcome of the BrightSpace modelling workshop).

Figure 5.: BrightSpace SJOS indicator modelling in CAPRI: coverage and modelling process

2.5. FarmDyn

FarmDyn is a versatile, mixed-integer bio-economic model designed to simulate optimal farm management and investment decisions under various market, technological, or policy scenarios. Developed by the Institute of Food and Resource Economics (ILR) at the University of Bonn, FarmDyn accommodates both comparative-static and fully dynamic analysis, with options for incorporating stochastic elements and different risk profiles. Its modular design allows for customisation to address specific research questions or regional needs.

Originally created for German farming systems, FarmDyn includes a comprehensive database covering field operations, crop calendars, yields, prices, costs, machinery specifications, and other essential data specific to German agriculture. Its detailed representation of dairy and cattle farming processes includes raising and fattening, grazing patterns, weight gains, calving and lactation periods for dairy cows, cross-breeding, and sexing options. FarmDyn also models diverse grassland management practices, manure management, and related storage and application techniques.

The model's investment modules use integer variables to represent investments in machinery, stables, and other farm structures. Labour requirements for various operations and maintenance tasks are accounted for, allowing for the endogenous representation of different-sized investments and labour-capital intensities. This capability leads to modelling increasing returns-to-scale in branch sizes, providing valuable insights into farm expansion and optimisation.

Initially developed through research projects, FarmDyn is currently maintained and enhanced by the ILR at Bonn University and is utilised by international partners. Quality management measures, including automated testing and a revision control system, ensure its reliability. Recent improvements have focused on broadening FarmDyn's applicability beyond Germany. Leveraging FADN data and enhanced code-data separation make the model increasingly adaptable to the Netherlands and other EU countries.

For a detailed description of the FARMDYN model, refer to Annex 1.

Figure 6 (a key outcome of the BrightSpace modelling workshop) visually illustrates how the FARMDYN model addresses BrightSpace SJOS indicator domains and their modelling processes.

Figure 6.: BrightSpace SJOS indicator modelling in FARMDYN: coverage and modelling process

2.6. IMAGE

The IMAGE 3.3 framework addresses critical global sustainability issues such as climate change, land-use change, biodiversity loss, nutrient cycle alterations, and water scarcity. These complex, long-term challenges often have global implications stemming from the ways human societies harness natural resources for energy, food, water, and shelter.

Economic growth, though bringing immense benefits, has also led to far-reaching changes in the global environment. Land clearing, biomass burning, intensive agriculture, and industrial emissions have profoundly altered natural systems. The scale of human impact has raised concerns about the Earth's ability to support a growing population and the potential for severe environmental degradation. Key policy challenges lie in reducing the negative effects of human activity on natural systems while aligning development goals with sustainability.

To understand these complex issues and design effective responses, integrated assessment models (IAMs) like IMAGE 3.3 are essential. IAMs describe critical interactions between human development and the natural environment, considering drivers, behaviours, and impacts. IAMs draw on functional relationships between human activities (e.g., food and energy production) and their associated environmental consequences. While traditionally focused on climate change and air pollution, IAMs are expanding to address a wider range of impacts, including water quality and scarcity, and resource depletion. They provide insights into how various factors drive impacts, taking into account feedback mechanisms.

IMAGE is a comprehensive IAM designed to analyse interactions between human and natural systems. Its objectives are:

- Analyse long-term global environmental change processes.
- Identify mitigation and adaptation strategies.
- Highlight key interlinkages and uncertainties.

IMAGE is often used to explore baseline and alternative scenarios:

- **Baseline Scenario:** Projects future outcomes under business-as-usual conditions, highlighting the costs of inaction and environmental impacts.
- **Alternative Scenarios:** Assess the effects of response strategies (e.g., climate change policies), revealing synergies and trade-offs between policy issues.

IAMs offer varying levels of complexity. IMAGE balances detail with simplicity to remain transparent and adaptable. It exists within a spectrum of models, ranging from those primarily focused on Earth systems to those focused on human systems (e.g., economic models).

Annex 1 provides a detailed description of the IMAGE model.

Figure 7 (a key outcome of the BrightSpace modelling workshop) provides a visual illustration of how the model addresses BrightSpace SJOS indicator domains and their modelling processes.

Figure 7.: BrightSpace SJOS indicator modelling in IMAGE: coverage and modelling process

3. BASELINE SCENARIO

3.1. Background from past projects

The baseline efforts under BrightSpace and LAMASUS did not have to start from scratch. On the contrary, several of the modelling systems have been used repeatedly in conjunction providing insights to build on.

3.1.1. EUCLIMIT series of service contracts with Commission DGs

Over more than a decade, a modelling cluster composed of GEM-E3, PRIMES, GLOBIOM, CAPRI, and GAINS prepared continuous updates of the EU reference scenario for sector-wide climate policies (European Commission, 2021). Two of these models (CAPRI, GLOBIOM) are also part of BrightSpace and LAMASUS such that the established mappings and interfaces provide an operational basis, at least for their bilateral interactions.

3.1.2. AGCLIM50 series of JRC projects

Over the last few years, JRC has initiated a series of small-budget projects, all focusing on various climate-related topics and involving MAGNET-IMAGE, GLOBIOM, and CAPRI (van Meijl et al., 2017). The weight of these studies had been amplified by active contributions from JRC staff and the choice of topics suitable for fine project publications (e.g., Frank et al. 2019, Hasegawa et al. 2018).

Furthermore, the JRC has also financed agri-food sector foresight studies exploring different futures using involving MAGNET-CAPRI (scenar2020, Scenar2030) (M'Barek et al., 2017). Aside from exploring different policy pathways for the EU CAP, these studies also required the use of harmonised baselines involving a series of model linkages.

The main benefits of these projects, apart from some specific model improvements, was the development of a strategy for efficient comparisons and exposition of model results from various modelling systems relying of modified versions of the “Agmip-Template” (see AGMIP, n.d.; von Lampe et al., 2014; Nelson et al., 2014). It turned out useful, for example, to compare model results mostly in terms of their developments against some reference year, given that the databases of large-scale systems are difficult to harmonise.

3.1.3. SSP preparation

Two Brightspace modelling systems (IMAGE and GLOBIOM) are also heavily involved in the process of developing the framework of Shared-Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios that have become the basis for thousands of studies in this area (Riahi et al., 2017) and are key input to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Projects 6 and 7 feeding into the different IPCC processes. An important benefit for BrightSpace of these activities is the easy access of relevant global data and information that is a context for projects with a European focus. In early 2024, an update of the original set of SSPs was published (Samir et al., 2024), including updated population and GDP projections for the five SSPs. The IMAGE, MAGNET and GLOBIOM teams will use these data to provide context to the analyses focused on the European scale.

3.1.4. SUPREMA

The Horizon 2000 project SUPREMA provided valuable experience in CAP and climate-related scenario work and a roadmap for future research activities. In the context of the toolbox concept of this WP it is also useful to remember the findings on model linkages. For specific pairs of models with clear

complementarities (like CAPRI and IFMCAP or AGMEMOD and MITERRA) the model linkage may provide considerable added value once the technical difficulties are mastered.

However, another finding was also that additional linkages do not always increase the overall consistency of results, if the definitions of items or methodologies are diverging a lot. This was a conclusion from linkage efforts exchanging selected model outputs between MAGNET, GLOBIOM and CAPRI (Gocht et al., 2020).

3.2. Purpose and results of fast-track baseline

For various reasons, it was decided to quickly prepare with the main large-scale BrightSpace models a simple business-as-usual baseline before waiting for model enhancements and detailed scenario planning. One of the reasons was that MAGNET, GLOBIOM and CAPRI were recently involved in modelling efforts under Agclim50v and EUCMILIT6 that appeared to permit a short preparation time.

3.2.1. Testing infrastructure for model comparisons

One of the advantages of a fast-track draft baseline was that it permits the test of dedicated IT infrastructure (“Accelerator”) developed by partner IIASA to facilitate handling, storage, archiving, comparing and analysing model outputs.

So far, the comparisons and result comparisons have been based on Excel pivot tables, which offer nice options for graphical display but are also time-consuming in the handling model outputs.

3.2.2. Identifying serious differences in BAU baselines

Even with the “traditional” comparisons based on pivot tables and comparisons of change indices against some base year, several problems have been identified:

- Macro data had not been fully aligned across modelling teams
- “Apparent” differences due to differences in reporting were identified and tackled (e.g., for the treatment of new energy crops in CAPRI)
- Serious differences in change indices for large world regions were identified [see Annex 2]
- As expected, a higher level of divergence was identified at the MS level. For the pair of GLOBIOM-CAPRI comparisons, this was partly due to a lack of updating model inputs from GLOBIOM

3.2.3. Harmonising model settings (e.g. MS coverage) and macro inputs

A common problem for all systems is an appropriate consideration of the new CAP SPs. Here it appears that AGMEMOD is currently most advanced in this process, but all toolbox models will need to reflect on the options to consider these CAP SPs in their system.

An important harmonisation was the decision to let MAGNET-IMAGE run at the level of single MS (with a few aggregates like Belgium and Luxembourg, and Greece, Cyprus and Malta).

For macro variables several email threads helped to identify and disseminate knowledge about differences between SSP2 projections and Aglink projections that had been tentatively selected as the standards source at the Rennes meeting unless there are significant drawbacks.

3.3. Ongoing improvements from consortium discussions

3.3.1. Discussion on sources for macro variables

Related to the discussion on macro variables the JRC (Aglink) macro variables as used in the 2023 DG AGRI outlook have been compared with the macro assumptions as embedded in the newly prepared SSPs. It appeared that the differences were considerably smaller than between Aglink projections and the older SSPs simply because similar historical data were inputs to the underlying estimates. However, basic issues have not been finally settled:

- If Aglink is not considered the original source for referencing, then the underlying sources have to be clarified. This is a small set of sources and therefore possible but the overlay takes into account various criteria to pick the best information available at the point of preparing the AGRI outlook and thus remains partly flexible and hence non-transparent
- The updated SSPs take the macro assumptions from two models only which is nice for referencing. Yet this may be somewhat inflexible in case that new events become known after completing the projections (like the Ukrainian war)
- The official DG-Clima GECO projections to 2050 (Keramidas et al. 2023) should be considered in the Aglink outlook
- For precise formula for extending the JRC provided information beyond its current horizon (2040) some approval was emerging from a joint BrightSpace-LAMASUS baseline meeting on April 18, 2024 to the following IIASA proposal: In order to make use country-level information in the (new) SSP projections their historical data for year 2000 were adopted as a starting point. Up to 2040 this starting point may be extended with growth as given from Aglink or from the more detailed underlying JRC data provided to the consortium. Change factors from Aglink/JRC may also be applied (with some inaccuracy) to all single countries combined in one Aglink aggregate. After 2040, these series will be extended with growth factors from the new SSPs

3.3.2. Completing indicator coverage on existing BAU baseline

An exchange took place to identify relevant indicators that could be provided by one or several modelling systems. Examples are the N and P surplus results or the BII as a well-known indicator for biodiversity assessments.

3.3.3. Discussing issues for baseline enhancement beyond business-as-usual

Since the proposal phase, it has been repeatedly discussed which other baseline developments should be factored in the Brightspace – LAMASUS baselines. Given the EU focus, all modelling systems have agreed to acknowledge the MS level CAP SPs in some form, but due to the different focus the emphasis was different. The greatest effort has been made in the AGMEMOD team and here it has led to a new model version that is not able anymore to provide a without-CAP-SP (BAU) baseline as most of the other models have done under the “fast-track” heading. The CAPRI team has also planned to develop a rather detailed representation but the required reorganisation of its policy module is still ongoing. The GLOBIOM team is still waiting for the CAPRI example to assess if this could provide an efficient strategy to deal with the full set of information that combines thousands of single measures but likely representation will be covered implicitly via calibration to the Aglink baseline that includes the CAP-SP. In the case of MAGNET, a mapping procedure has been performed recently between the array of CAP SP market support and rural development payments and the recipient activities and relevant

drivers (i.e., land-based, capital-based, input-based), although this was not prepared in time for the fast-track baseline.

Another medium-run (or perhaps long-run) topic is the recent surge of various energy prices as it had been repeatedly presented by a member of the scientific advisory board (T. Haniotis) at the opportunity of the European Association of Agricultural Economics (EAAE) pre-congress seminar in Rennes and at the baseline meeting attached to the LAMASUS annual meeting in the Hague. While it was accepted to acknowledge these new developments it appears that none of the modelling systems is able to reorganise the database in the BrightSpace context to also zoom into the details of energy price developments (e.g. regarding oil vs. gas prices).

While it has been accepted to also consider a variant with climate change no further details have been decided yet (Which RCP? With or without CO₂ fertilisation, etc.). Similarly, it has been accepted to reflect the Ukrainian war in some way, but not how this element should look like (full EU accession? With what timeline?). Accession of the Western Balkan countries is probably a less dramatic change, but exactly for this reason also more likely to happen in the next years

3.4. Preparation of stakeholder involvement in first retreat

The first retreat on June 19-20, 2024 in Leuven has two main objectives

- The first objective is to collect feedback on the fast-track baseline as well as on a list of uncertainties or challenges that have a reasonable likelihood to materialise.
- The second objective is to present to stakeholders the preliminary set of SJOS indicators that have been quantified in the context of the fast-track baseline and to stimulate feedback on the state of indicator development.

In line with this plan, an agenda has been developed that offers an opportunity for this desired feedback. The work under WPs 5 and 11 are closely interlinked (and more details are given in D11.1): On the one hand, the stakeholder interaction benefits from the illustrative baseline preparation, which may provoke more lively discussion on the results than in a purely hypothetical context. On the other hand, the current baseline preparation is to some extent still open, particularly for the longer run perspective (up to 2070), such that stakeholder feedback may be picked up if it is considered relevant by the respective modelling experts.

4. NEXT STEPS AND CONCLUSION

The bulk of the model improvements will happen in dedicated work packages focusing on specific aspects, say the coverage of biodiversity impacts.

This “toolbox work package” has a coordination role that is important for the overall modelling work with the following contributions:

1. The diagrams on model functionality were developed in a dedicated seminar in a limited amount of time. Some standardisation and perhaps simplification may increase their accessibility and hence provide better input for dissemination and stakeholder communication.
2. This work package may identify topic areas that are still insufficiently covered and could be tackled by at least one system either under BrightSpace, under supplementary running project or in future projects.
3. If some topic areas are covered by several systems, it should be decided at some point what the “leading” model in this area should be, at least when later selecting the key results of BrightSpace.
4. The empirical work on several aspects of technologies, consumer behaviour and policies in WP 3 and 4 often starts at Month 6 and extends to Month 36, meaning that at the end of Reporting Period 1, the focus has been on the methodology and conceptual framework as presented in the respective publication projects. Empirical results becoming available later may be picked up in the scenario work and possibly also in refinements of the baseline.

There is a risk of interference or double work with other WPs like WP6 on “Safe model upgrades and indicators” such that this WP should mainly collect the information from other WPs and check it for completeness and consistency. Yet, as other WPs are often looking at specific issues, this WP has some role to play to ensure that the emerging toolbox really fits to the ambition of Brightspace.

The immediate next step for WP 5 will be the coordination of baseline updates that should be presented to stakeholders in the first retreat, organised and planned in its communication elements under WP11.

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ANNEX 1: MODEL FACT SHEETS

MAGNET - Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool

Summary

MAGNET is a recursive dynamic, multi-region, multi-sector Computable General Equilibrium model used to analyse policy scenarios on agricultural economics, bioeconomy, food security, and international trade. It was developed by the Wageningen Economic Research (WEER) in cooperation with JRC and the Thünen Institute.

MAGNET is calibrated to the GTAP database and describes production, use and international trade flows of goods and services and primary factor use differentiated by sectors. The database distinguishes 140 countries or regions (including all EU member states), 57 sectors (plus several possible extensions) and 8 factors (e.g., labour, capital, land). A distinguishing feature of the model is its modular design which allows tailoring its structure to the research question. The GTAP model forms the MAGNET core while users choose among several extensions: different nesting structures or assumptions about factor markets, different agricultural-, trade- and biofuels-policy mechanisms and different assumptions relating to investment allocation. Other modules deal with the representation of the Common Agricultural Policies (including rural development), land and labour supply, production quotas, tariff rate quotas, biofuels directive, water in agriculture to name a few.

MAGNET can be used in policy formulation through ex-ante policy analysis. The model assess policy scenarios related to agriculture and agri-food trade and takes into account other fields strictly connected with agriculture such-as bioeconomy (bioenergy, biofuel...), sustainable use of resources (land and water), food security and nutrition (developing and developed countries) and climate change. Policy scenarios are compared against a baseline including the most recent macroeconomic (GDP and population) and agricultural (yields, land productivity, EU agricultural mid-term outlook) exogenous drivers. Scenario analysis might enter impact assessment of policy under stake. Focusing on ex-ante policy analysis, the model can be used to support policy formulation or to provide valuable information to policy makers in front of exogenous shocks.

Keywords: *trade policy, CAP, multi-commodity model, baseline, bioeconomy, agricultural economic model, Food Security, recursive-dynamic, global model*

Model type: *Comparative statistic, Computable general equilibrium (CGE), Dynamic, General equilibrium*

Ownership:

Multiple copyright: The MAGNET consortium, led by Wageningen Economic Research, includes the Institute for Prospective Technological Studies (IPTS), which is an institute of the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the Thünen-Institute (TI).

Code sharing and license:

License type: Non-Free Software licence. The license has one or more of the following restrictions: it prohibits creation of derivative works; it prohibits commercial use; it obliges to share the licensed or derivative works on the same conditions.

Specific licence: Other non-free licence

Details: MAGNET needs GEMPACK software which is copyrighted by GEMPACK Software (<https://www.copsmodels.com/gp-lictext.htm>)

More about the model under: <https://www.magnet-model.eu/>

Details on MAGNET structure and approach

The Modular Agricultural GeNeral Equilibrium Tool (MAGNET) is a multi-region computable general equilibrium model which is a derivative of the well-known Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) model. It is developed and applied at Wageningen Economic Research (WEER) at the University of Wageningen and is also employed by the Thünen Institute (TI) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC/D).

MAGNET is calibrated to the latest version of the GTAP database which describes production, use and international trade flows of goods and services, as well as primary factor use differentiated by sectors. The GTAP database distinguishes 140 countries or regions (among them the 28 EU member states), 57 sectors and 8 factor endowments. It is based on country input-output tables and includes consistent bilateral trade flows, transport and protection data. Additional datasets are used for specific MAGNET modules, among them data coming from the International Energy Agency (IEA), the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), the Clearance Audit Trail System (CATS) database for CAP analysis. The choice of regions and sectors from the database can be flexibly aggregated to set-up specific model versions.

MAGNET consists of a system of three types of equations. Firstly, 'behavioural equations' employing 'convenient' mathematical functions represent, under conditions of constrained optimisation, the theoretical tenets of neoclassical economic demand and supply. Subject to a series of 'market clearing' (i.e., supply equals demand) and 'accounting' equations (i.e., income equals expenditure equals output; zero 'economic' profits) consistent with the underlying accounting conventions of the database, the model enforces 'equilibrium'. To solve the model, the number of equations and (endogenous) variables within the system must be the same (known as the model 'closure'). Additional variables under the direct control of the modeller (defined as 'exogenous'), which capture market imperfections (tax rates), factor endowments or technological change, can be manipulated or 'shocked', whereupon the model finds a new matrix of prices and quantities to arrive at a post-shock equilibrium subject to the aforementioned accounting and market clearing restrictions.

A key strength of the MAGNET model is that it allows the user to choose a la carte those sub-modules of relevance to a specific study. The user can (inter alia) choose between different nesting structures, apply different assumptions about the workings of the factor markets, include different agricultural-, trade- and biofuels-policy mechanisms and incorporate dynamic assumptions relating to investment allocation over time periods.

To characterise the peculiarities of agricultural markets, the model accounts for the heterogeneity of land usage by agricultural activity; a regional endogenous land supply function; the sluggish mobility of capital and labour transfer between agricultural and non-agricultural sectors with associated wage and rent differentials; the inclusion of explicit substitution possibilities between different feed inputs in the livestock sectors; and additional behavioural and accounting equations to characterise EU agricultural policy mechanisms (e.g., production quotas, single farm payment, coupled payments, rural development measures). For the CAP module, additional coupled and decoupled policy variables are included to allow for a finer representation of CAP policy shocks. Furthermore, a detailed set of CAP policy payments, taken from the Clearance of Accounts Audit Trail System (CATS) database (DG AGRI) are used as a basis for calculating 'CAP reference scenario' shocks. In addition, an 'own-resources' module is included within the CAP budget accounting equations. Further modelling enhancements are incorporated including of 'first' and 'second' generation biofuels, GHG emission, water indicators. Other modules include treatment of waste, enhancement of labour market, fishery, inclusion of other climate policies and damage function and a specific module on SDGs indicators.

The results of the MAGNET model are typically presented in value terms or in price and quantity percentage changes. The MAGNET model compiles a large number of indicators, in particular related to production, trade flows, consumption, use of endowments, intermediate input use, income and price changes, land use, emissions, employment. As an additional tool of analysis, this study draws on

the GEMPACK decomposition method. On running a complex scenario with an array of shocks (i.e., endowments, tariffs, technology change etc.), it is possible to calculate the part-worth of the resulting endogenous variable change that corresponds to a specific exogenous shock, or pre-specified group of exogenous shocks. Thus, when comparing each of the scenarios with the reference scenario, the comparative 'part-worth' importance of the four policy indicators is evaluated in order to better understand the role that policy has to play (if any) in shaping bio-based market trends.

Baseline scenario

The MAGNET baseline scenario provides a basis to understand the scale and significance of global environmental problems and their connection to human activity. The scenario helps illustrate the potential consequences of inaction ('business as usual'), including future costs, missed opportunities, and the detrimental effects on nature from continuing current practices. The model includes some degree of endogenous feedback to account for impacts within the system. For Brightspace project the MAGNET baseline scenario is constructed using a benchmark year of 2017 and incorporates both historical and projected data. It is divided into three distinct periods: 2017-2020, 2020-2030, and 2030-2050. The initial period (2017-2020) focuses on accurately reflecting recent economic and political trends. Real GDP targets from SSP2 scenario are used to calibrate region wide technology change across all activities with scaling weights to calculate technology shifters for agriculture, manufacturing and services sector classifications. In addition, agricultural land productivity shocks consistent with a 'middle of the road' time trend are based on shared socio-economic pathway 2 (SSP2 – von Lampe et al, 2014). In the MAGNET model, labour force projections follow regional population trends (i.e., fixed medium to long-term employment rates); capital endowment growth rates are equal to regional macro growth forecasts (i.e., fixed medium to long-run capital-output ratio), whilst to avoid unrealistic supply price increases over medium-term time frames, the exploitation rate of the natural resource endowment is assumed to grow at one-quarter the rate of the change in the capital stock.

Input and parametrisation

Please list the key inputs used for the model.

- Value of Margins on international trade (GTAP database)
- Value of Bilateral imports and exports (GTAP database)
- Value of Intermediate and production factors use by industries (GTAP database)
- Value of commodity outputs (GTAP database)
- Value of Capital stock (GTAP database)
- Value of Tax revenues (GTAP database)
- Ad-valorem rate of several tax instruments (GTAP database)
- Income elasticities (GTAP database)
- Armington elasticities (GTAP database)
- Production elasticities (GTAP database)
- EU Agricultural Production and net trade (DG AGRI Agricultural Outlook)
- GHG emission for the (EU Reference Scenario 2016 on energy, transport and climate action)
- Land supply (FAOSTAT)
- CAP payments (CATS database)
- GDP and population projections (various sources)

Besides this list you may provide additional information on input and parametrisation, such as formats and sources.

The use of MAGNET requires, at a minimum, an understanding of the standard GTAP model and an ability to read GEMPACK code.

Main output

- Macroeconomic variables (GDP, welfare, value added, savings-investments, current account, world prices)
- Sectorial indicators (production, consumption, bilateral trade)
- Production factors (employment, wage, land use and price, capital)
- Additional indicators tailored on the study (water, bioenergy, biofuel, ...)
- Nutrition indicators
- Sustainable Development Goals Indicators

MAGNET analyses the economy-wide and distributional impacts of policy and/or structural shocks, sectoral transmission of sector-specific policies for sectors, agents and regions. The output of MAGNET includes projections of input-output tables, GDP, employment, bilateral trade, capital flows and household consumption. The explicit formulation of representative households allows the derivation of welfare indicators

The output has the following spatial-temporal resolution and extent:

Parameter	Description
Spatial Extent / Country Coverage	Global
(Spatial) resolution	Country level (160 countries)
Temporal extent	Base year 2017, can run in time step up to 2100.
Temporal resolution	To be selected by the modellers, minimum 1 year.

Relationships with other models

MAGNET..	ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
provides optional input to	STAGE-DEV	Results such as world price changes can be taken from MAGNET scenarios and used as shocks into STAGE_DEV.
is based on	RUNGAP	MAGNET is based on the GTAP model, which forms the core of MAGNET.
has an instance operated by	iMAP	
can use output from	AGLINK-COSIMO	Data on EU agricultural production and net trade used to calibrate the model
can use output from	CAPRI	Change in EU MS production, EU trade can be used as input for MAGNET
can use output from	IMAGE	Land use data. The IMAGE crop and land-use models supply information to MAGNET on land supply by region and changes in potential yields
can use output from	PRIMES	GHG emissions data can be used as input

MAGNET..	ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
can potentially be linked to	AGLINK-COSIMO	Results from MAGNET has been passed to AGLINK for scenario analysis of trade agreement.
can potentially be linked to	AGMEMOD	AGRICISTRATE (FP7 project) looks into this link.
can potentially be linked to	CAPRI	MAGNET sends to CAPRI changes in the EU agricultural productivity linked to rural development payment. Change in EU MS production, EU trade can be used as input for MAGNET.
can potentially be linked to	RUSLE2015	The outputs of RUSLE2015 have been inserted in MAGNET in order to make an estimation of the soil erosion costs at global scale

Relationships with datasets

MAGNET...	Related dataset	Origin	Details of the relationship
requires as input	GTAP Data Base	Global Analysis (GTAP) Trade Project	GTAP is the core part of the model database
creates as output	FTA - Free trade agreements study	JRC	Results of a study performed with MAGNET
creates as output	Scenar 2030	JRC	Results of a study performed with MAGNET (among other models)
can use as input	Land	FAO	To calibrate MAGNET land function
can use as input	Population Estimates and Projections	World Bank (WB)	To Calibrate MAGNET baseline population growth.

Quality, reliability & transparency

Quality and reliability

Criterion	Is the criterion met?	Details
Have uncertainties been quantified in the model runs?	no	Not accounted for systematically, but most relevant ones tested via additional simulations
Has the model undergone sensitivity analysis?	yes	Scenarios to account mainly sensitivity are usually added to main analyses
Has the model undergone external peer review (by a panel of experts)?	no	There has been no formal evaluation of the model by an external panel, however the model has been extensively published in peer-reviewed journals and is widely regarded as state-of-the-art global Computable General Equilibrium of agricultural and bioeconomy analysis.
Has model validation been done? Model predictions have been confronted with observed data (ex-post analysis).	no	Projections are not the main objective of the model, the model's strength lays in analysing deviations from baseline (i.e. projections) due to external shocks (policy or other)

Peer-review for model quality and reliability (panel review or peer-review in scientific journals):

- Not Provided

Transparency

Criterion	Meets criterion	Details
Is the model input data / underlying database (i.e. the database the model runs are based on) made publicly available?	no	The underlying database GTAP is not public available
Can model outputs be made publicly available?	yes	Through publications in reports and journals, as well as i the data platform dataM.
Are model equations and data base transparently documented and are these documents available to the general public?	yes	See model documentation
Is the model source code publicly accessible?	no	The original code is owned by 3rd party and not publicly available. The MAGNET consortium, led by Wageningen Economic Reserach (WEER), includes JRC and the Thünen-Institute (TI).

References related to documentation:

- [Assessing potential coupling factors of European decoupled payments with the Modular Agricultural GeNeral Equilibrium Tool \(MAGNET\)](#)

Policy relevance and intended role in the policy cycle

The model is designed to contribute to the following policy areas:

- Agriculture
- Biobased economy
- Trade
- Food security
- Circular economy
- Economic and Monetary Affairs
- Energy
- Environment
- Climate policies
- Regional Policy

And the following phases of the policy cycle:

- Formulation

Details

This economic simulation model, as a contribution to this impact assessment process, can provide insights into the effects of different policy scenarios on international trade and competitiveness.

The model is designed to conduct policy experiments, in which a reference scenario or baseline is first simulated over a future period and then, after changing one or more underlying assumptions (all kind

of police instruments, tax, tariffs...), a new scenario incorporating these changes is run, also over the same time period. Comparison of the new scenario with the reference scenario at a given point in the simulation period, usually in terms of percentage differences, establishes the direction and relative magnitude of the impacts on all the endogenous variables of the change that is depicted in the hypothetical scenario at that point in time.

Impact areas that the model can help to assess

Impact types that can be assessed with the models include:

Impact area	Category	Subcategory	Can be assessed by MAGNET through
Economic	Operating costs and conduct of business	Adjustment, compliance or transaction costs	<i>Change in use of production factors and intermediate inputs</i>
Economic	Operating costs and conduct of business	Cost/availability of essential inputs (raw materials, machinery, labour, energy, ..)	<i>Change in the cost of intermediate inputs</i>
Economic	Operating costs and conduct of business	Affects on individual Member States	<i>All outputs can be reported at MS level</i>
Economic	Trade and investment flows	EU Exports & imports	<i>Change in bilateral trade volume and prices against rest of the world and intra EU trade</i>
Economic	Trade and investment flows	Non-trade barriers	<i>Impacts of changes of NTM on the model outputs</i>
Economic	Trade and investment flows	Third countries	<i>Impacts of changes of standards on model outputs</i>
Economic	Competitiveness (sectoral) of business	Market share & advantages in international context	<i>Market share by commodity by exports in each importing country</i>
Economic	Consumers and households	Consumer's ability to benefit from the internal market or to access goods and services from outside the EU	<i>Prices of domestic and foreign goods and services</i>
Economic	Consumers and households	Prices, quality, availability or choice of consumer goods and services	<i>Prices of domestic and foreign goods and services</i>
Economic	Specific regions or sectors	Significant effects on sectors	<i>Change of output and value added by sectors</i>
Economic	Specific regions or sectors	Impact on regions	<i>Change in employment level by sector and Member State</i>
Economic	Specific regions or sectors	Disproportionately affected region or sector	<i>All output available at Member State level</i>
Economic	Third countries and international relations	EU foreign policy and EU development policy	<i>Impacts on selected third countries (macro, welfare, GDP) of each EU policy</i>
Economic	Third countries and international relations	Impacts on third countries	<i>Impacts on selected third countries (macro, welfare, GDP) of each EU policy</i>
Economic	Third countries and international relations	Impacts on developing countries	<i>Impacts on selected third countries (macro, welfare, GDP) of each EU policy</i>

Impact area	Category	Subcategory	Can be assessed by MAGNET through
Economic	Third countries and international relations	Adjustment costs in developing countries	<i>Change in use of production factors and intermediate inputs in selected third countries</i>
Economic	Third countries and international relations	Goods traded with developing countries	<i>Change in production at sectorial level in selected third countries</i>
Economic	Macroeconomic environment	Economic growth and employment	<i>Impacts on economic growth in selected third countries</i>
Environmental	Climate	Emission of greenhouse gases	<i>Changes in emission by gas and by sector</i>
Environmental	International environmental impacts	Environment in third countries	<i>Changes in emission by gas and by sector</i>
Environmental	Transport and the use of energy	Energy intensity of the economy	<i>Level of energy intensity by sector</i>
Environmental	Land use	Change in land use	<i>Land use in the EU and selected third countries</i>
Social	Employment	Impact on jobs	<i>Number of jobs</i>
Social	Employment	Impact on jobs in specific sectors, professions, regions or countries	<i>Number of jobs in each Member State in each sector</i>
Social	Working Conditions	Wages, labour costs or wage setting mechanisms	<i>Changes in wage level</i>

Connection to existing indicator classification schemes: (e.g. SDGs, SJOS, ...)

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
Real	SDG8
	SDG1
# Index of per capita utility from private expend. in region r#;	SDG1
# Value of agricultural factor payments updated with prices #;	SDG1
# Total value of agri unskilled labour payments updated with prices #;	SDG1
# Average unskilled agricultural wage in region r #;	SDG1
# Total value of cereal consumption updated with prices #	SDG1
# Private consumption price for cereals in region r #;	SDG1
GDPPcLev	SDG17
ProdTaxShGDP	SDG17
FactTaxShGDP	SDG17
SaleTaxShGDP	SDG17
TradTaxShGDP	SDG17
Air pollution elements of the SDG11 indicator table	SDG11
airpol assoc with output in Ggrams	SDG11

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
airpol assoc with int input in Ggrams#	SDG11
airpol assoc with HH in Ggrams	SDG11
airpol assoc with endow in Ggrams	SDG11
air pol from biomass burning in Ggrams	SDG11
REGion-wide by Air Pollution by Type in Ggrams	SDG11
Total region wide air pollution in Ggrams	SDG11
REGion-wide by Air Pollution by Type in Kg per capita	SDG11
% change in air pollution	SDG11
% change in air pollution per capita	SDG11
SDG12 indicator over ShRenewEnPr, FosSubShGDP, FosSubShFExp i.e. share of renewables in total energy prod, amount of fossil fuels subsidies per unit of GDP, amount of fossil fuel subsidies as share of national expenditure on fossils	SDG12
SDG15 share of non agri land proxy for forest area	SDG15
SDG15 share of non agri land proxy for forest area	SDG15
SDG8 sustainable and inclusive economic growth	SDG8
regional annual growth rate of gdp per capita	SDG8
EVFP equivalent	SDG8
Value added of aggregated sector group over total value added	SDG8
SDG inequality (composed on wage and employment)	SDG10
Total value of agri skilled labour payments updated with prices	SDG10
Average skilled agricultural wage in region r	SDG10
Value of non-agricultural factor payments updated with prices	SDG10
Total value of non-agri unskilled labour payments updated with prices	SDG10
Average unskilled non-agricultural wage in region r	SDG10
Total value of non-agri skilled labour payments updated with prices	SDG10
Average skilled non-agricultural wage in region r	SDG10
size of EDUC_COMM set	SDG10
expenditure on education	SDG10
total final expenditure	SDG10
education expenditure share on final demand	SDG10
SDG10 wealth and inequality share variables	SDG10
SDG10 wealth and inequality share variables	SDG10

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
Drivers SDG10 (EDUshr,AGRVAshr,INDVAshr,TIME,GDPPC,TRDSHRGDP)	SDG10
SDG10 wealth and inequality share variables	SDG10
Regional income per capita	SDG10
	SDG10
SDG ID (income decile) Eurostat	SDG10
Regional income per capita	SDG10
scaling deciles	SDG10
	SDG10
Eurostat GDPpc in euros 2014 prices by EU MS normalised#;	SDG10 - SDG5
Eurostat Labour (with JRC split) (thousands) using wittgenstein region-wide shocks to gender and skill	SDG10 - SDG5
proj changes in workforce by education, gender and region	SDG10 - SDG5
Eurostat Labour (with JRC split) (thousands) control for total	SDG10
workforce by education, activity and region control for total	SDG10
gender share weights by skill and activity	SDG10 - SDG5
% chnge in Eurostat Lab (JRC split) (thousands)	SDG10 - SDG5
Eurostat Labour (with JRC split) (thousands)	SDG10 - SDG5
Eurostat Labour (thousands) updated with wittgenstein region-wide shocks to gender and skill	SDG10 - SDG5
proj changes in workforce by gender and region	SDG10 - SDG5
Eurostat Labour (thousands) control total	SDG10
workforce by activity and region control total	SDG10
Share weights Eurostat Labour	SDG10 - SDG5
% chnge in Eurostat Labour (thousands)	SDG10 - SDG5
Eurostat EU populations (in thousands of persons)	SDG10
Eurostat GDP (in millions euros 2014 market prices)	SDG10
Eurostat EU GDP (in millions euros 2014 market prices)	SDG10
Eurostat EU population (in thousands of persons)	SDG10
Eurostat GDPpc in euros 2014 prices by EU MS#;	SDG10
Eurostat GDPpc in euros 2014 prices EU27 average	SDG10
Eurostat GDPpc in euros 2014 prices by EU MS normalised#;	SDG10

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
Region Fisheries as a value share of GDP	SDG14
Indicator for SDG4 as share of skilled workers	SDG4
pop projections by gender cohort 20-24	SDG4
population by gender	SDG4
SDG4 variable	SDG4
change in sdg4 variable	SDG4
SDG4 variables for calibration (calibrated error)	SDG4
SDG4 coefficient	SDG4
SDG4 coefficient	SDG4
BIRTHPER1000, SR_NBORN100, SR_CHILD100, LIFE_EXP	SDG3
GDPpc,EDUyr,AGRshr,OPEN,PALMA,GDPpc_sq,PCFD,PCFD_SQ,PC_AIRP	SDG3
SDG3 variable	SDG3
SDG3 variables for calibration	SDG3
SDG3 coefficient	SDG3
SDG3 Variable	SDG3
DomFdPrAg, DomFdPrAgFi,FoodImports, FoodExports, CalsPcPd,CalsPcPdXFsh, ShCalCer, ProtGrPcPd, ProtGrPcPdXF, DisplncPCK, FoodPrices, ShFoodExp, FoodCons, PcFoodCons, ShCalFruVeg, BMlaverage,BMlunderwght,BMlnormwght,BMloverwght, BMlObese1,BMlObese2,BMlObese3, TFP, AvAgTariff, AvAgExpSub, AvTariffAgPC, AvExpSubAgPC	SDG2
SDG2 coefficient	SDG2
Value of commodity i output in region r at agent's prices base year	SDG2
Quantity of domestic primary agricultural production	SDG2
Domestic primary agricultural production	SDG2
Index of quantity of domestic primary agricultural production	SDG2
Quantity of domestic primary agricultural and fish production	SDG2
Domestic primary agricultural and fish production	SDG2
Index of quantity of domestic primary agricultural production	SDG2
Quantity of food imports by region	SDG2
Average food imports by region quantity	SDG2
Food import quantity index	SDG2
Quantity of food exports by region	SDG2
Average food exports by region quantity	SDG2
Food export quantity index	SDG2
Value of food consumption updated with price changes	SDG2
Average food price by region	SDG2
Food price index	SDG2
Value of consumption updated with quantities	SDG2
Total value of food consumption updated with quantities	SDG2
Average food consumption by region	SDG2

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
Food consumption quantity index	SDG2
Population	SDG2
Population	SDG2
Total value of food consumption per capita updated with quantities	SDG2
Average food consumption per capita by region	SDG2
Food consumption quantity per capita index	SDG2
kilo calories per capita per day Region Body Mass Index Side Calculations	SDG2
initial BMI means y EU MS Eurostat micro data	SDG2
Constant correction term in the function for EU27 MS	SDG2
Constant correction term in the function for EU27 MS	SDG2
initial BMI means by EU MS based on Eurostat micro data based on the Springmann et al. Function	SDG2
Cutoff intervals BMI after Box-Cox transf	SDG2
Box-Cox transformation parameter for each MS probab dist	SDG2
Transformed Box-Cox BMI means in each region	SDG2
percentage change in the std dev. by region	SDG2
St. dev after Box Cox transformation	SDG2
changing st.dev. of cutoff points as mean shifts	SDG2
Dispersion of population by BMI category. Expressed as %	SDG2
With a mean of 0 and st. dev of 1, the CUMNORMAL function takes	
the integral under the normal distribution in two halves	
(i.e., $+\infty$ to zero is 50% area and $-\infty$ to zero is 50%).	
Average dispersion	SDG2
Size of GREG set i.e. regions without aknreg for productivity calculation of indicator SDG2	SDG2
producer expenditure on i by j in r at mkt prices updated with quantities	SDG2
Total endowment spending updated with quantities	SDG2
Total endowment spending updated with quantities in agg regions	SDG2
Weighted technical change in aggregate regions	SDG2
Index of endowment enhancing technc change in region r for baseline	SDG2
Initial average agricultural tariff for subsidy and tax calculation	SDG2
Initial average agricultural export subsidy	SDG2
PrimEnergy, ShRenew, FinalEnergy, EnSelfSuff, EnPriceFoss, EnPriceRenBF, EnPriceRenOt, EnPriceNucl, FossComp, RenewComp, VAEnContr, Land1GenBiof, Land2GenBiof, LandBioEly, VADoEnAgriFe, VADoEnFood, VADoEnFosFu, VADoEnBioRen, VADoEnEly, VADoEnManu, VADoEnServ, PrimEnGDP, RefinEnGDP, FinalEnGDP, FinEnPrimEn, ShHhldExpEn	SDG7
Energy sectors - placing in categories	SDG7
Gas commodities	SDG7
Coal commodities	SDG7
quantity of priv (hh) cons of domestic good i in region s	SDG7

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
quantity of priv (hh) cons of imported good i in region s	SDG7
Efficiency ratio of secondary energy i production region r	SDG7
Quantity of energy i production	SDG7
Quantity of primary energy i production	SDG7
Quantity of exported of good i from region r to s	SDG7
Quantity of energy i imported by region s	SDG7
Use of energy quantity i in region s	SDG7
Use of domestic energy quantity i in region s	SDG7
Use of imported energy quantity i in region s	SDG7
Firms use of domestic energy quantity i in region s	SDG7
Firms use of imported energy quantity i in region s	SDG7
Domestic energy i quantity priv cons in region s	SDG7
Imported energy i quantity priv cons in region s	SDG7
Domestic energy i quantity gov. cons in region s	SDG7
Imported energy i quantity gov. cons in region s	SDG7
Domestic use energy balance	SDG7
Imported use energy balance	SDG7
World energy balance	SDG7
Domestic use energy balance	SDG7
Imported use energy balance	SDG7
World energy balance	SDG7
Domestic use energy balance	SDG7
Imported use energy balance	SDG7
World energy balance	SDG7
Domestic sales of crude oil energies in region 'r'	SDG7
export sales of crude oil energies in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of crude oil energies in region 'r'	SDG7
total available crude oil energies in region 'r'	SDG7
Domestic sales of coal energies in region 'r'	SDG7
export sales of coal energies in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of coal energies in region 'r'	SDG7
total available coal energies in region 'r'	SDG7
Domestic sales of gas energies in region 'r'	SDG7
export sales of gas energies in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of gas energies in region 'r'	SDG7
total available gas energies in region 'r'	SDG7
Domestic sales of bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7
export sales of bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
import needs of bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7
total available bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7
Domestic sales of renewables energies in region 'r'	SDG7
export sales of renewables energies in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of renewables energies in region 'r'	SDG7
total available renewables energies in region 'r'	SDG7
Domestic sales of bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7
export sales of bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7
total available bio energies in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of petroleum in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of electricity in region 'r'	SDG7
import needs of electricity in region 'r'	SDG7
Total energy stocks available in 'r' (dom demand,exports,imports)	SDG7
kerosene refining	SDG7
petroleum refining	SDG7
Input needs of electricity generation in region 'r'	SDG7
Total refining and generation usage of energy commodities in region 'r'	SDG7
Transport usage of energy in region 'r'	SDG7
Industry usage of energy commodities in region 'r'	SDG7
Non-refining energy inputs of refining sectors	SDG7
Industry usage of energy commodities in region 'r'	SDG7
Other usage of Energy commodities in region 'r'	SDG7
export sales of refined energies in region 'r'	SDG7
total final usage of Energy commodities in region 'r'	SDG7
Total energy i quantity production in region 'r'	SDG7
Total final domestic usage of energy commodities in region 'r'	SDG7
Share of biofuels and renewables in total blended inputs	SDG7
Total final usage of renewable and biofuel energy commodities in region 'r'	SDG7
Index of total available energy stocks per unit of GDP	SDG7
Index of total refining and generation energy use per unit of GDP	SDG7
Index of total final usage of energy commodities per unit of GDP	SDG7
Index of total final usage of energy commodities per unit of primary en	SDG7
Total value of output of fossil sectors	SDG7
Fossil supply price by region	SDG7
Index of fossil supply price by region	SDG7
Total value of output of renewable biofuel sectors	SDG7
Renewable biofuel supply price by region	SDG7

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
Index of renewable biofuel supply price by region	SDG7
Total value of output of other renewable sectors	SDG7
Other renewables supply price by region	SDG7
Index of other renewables supply price by region	SDG7
Total value of output of nuclear sectors	SDG7
Nuclear supply price by region	SDG7
Index of nuclear supply price by region	SDG7
Ratio of value added to domestic energy use	SDG7
market price index of primary factors, by region	SDG7
GDP price index by region including aggregates	SDG7
Real mkt price index of primary factors, by r	SDG7
Total value of output of all renewable sectors	SDG7
Renewables supply price by region	SDG7
Equals VDFM	SDG7
Makebcom	SDG7
land demand	SDG7
dummy for biodisel	SDG7
dummy for bioely	SDG7
dummy for biofuel that use land except biodisel	SDG7
Use of land using inputs by biofuel sector	SDG7
crude vegetable oil	SDG7
shares of biofuels use	SDG7
share of crude veg oil	SDG7
cvol use	SDG7
cvol share	SDG7
Land demand for biofuel inputs	SDG7
Land demand for biodiesel inputs	SDG7
Land dedicated to bioenergy km2	SDG7
Land dedicated to biodiesel km2	SDG7
ManVASH, ManVAPc, ShManEmp, CrpsCO2VaS, CrpsCombVaS, CrpsNCombVaS, LvStCO2VaS, LvStCombVaS, LvStNCombVaS, TotalImports, TotalExports, TradeOpen	SDG9
SDG9 indicators	SDG9
dummy for industrial production	SDG9
Share of emissions by type and ag sector per unit of value added	SDG9
Quantity of imports by region	SDG9
Average imports by region quantity	SDG9
Quantity of exports by region	SDG9
Average imports by region quantity	SDG9

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
AgWaterUse	SDG6a
SDG6 indicators	SDG6
Total abstracted irrigation water volumes in r	SDG6
Total abstracted irrigation water volumes in r	SDG6
Total abstracted irrigation water volumes in r	SDG6
Index of total abstracted irrigation water volumes in r	SDG6
AgWaterUse, IrrLandShr	SDG6
SDG6 indicators	SDG6
Total abstracted irrigation water volumes in r	SDG6
Total abstracted irrigation water volumes in r	SDG6
Index of total abstracted irrigation water volumes in r	SDG6
RegBF1Dir, RegBF2Dir, RegBioeDir, RegBFaviDir, SHEMISGDP, EmisPerCal, EmisPerCalPc, ShRenewEnPr, VAshAgriFeed, VAshFood, VAshFosFuEn, VAshBioREn, VAshEly, VAshManu, VAshServ, VACoShAgFeed, VACoShFood, VACoShFosEn, VACoShBioREn, VACoShEly, VACoShManu, VACoShServ	SDG13
Share of sector value added in total value added	SDG13
value of sector j output in region r at agent's prices	SDG13
Share of sector value added in total costs	SDG13
ShFishGDP	SDG14
SDG14 indicators	SDG14

Use of MAGNET by clients

NL:

- Ministry of Agriculture
- Ministry of Economic Affairs

EU:

- In-house mode of JRC Seville
- It is **currently** actively in use or followed by the following **policy DGs**:
 - Directorate-General for Trade [TRADE]
 - Directorate-General for International Cooperation and Development [DEVCO]
 - Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development [AGRI]
 - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation [RTD]

International organisations:

- OECD
- FAO
- CGIAR

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GLOBIOM

The Global Biosphere Management Model (GLOBIOM) is an economic model designed to address various land use related topics (bioenergy policy impacts, deforestation dynamics, climate change adaptation and mitigation from agriculture, long term agricultural prospect).

Summary

The Global Biosphere Management Model (GLOBIOM) is a partial-equilibrium model representing main land use sectors, including agriculture and forestry. The supply side of the model is built from the bottom (spatially explicit land cover, land use, management systems and economic cost information) to the top (regional commodity markets). Demand is determined at the level of aggregate regions. Food demand projections are based on the interaction of three different drivers: population growth, per-capita income growth, and response to prices (based on consumer preferences), and policies. The spatial resolution of the supply side relies on the concept of Simulation Units that are aggregates of 5 to 30 arcmin pixels belonging to the same altitude, slope, and soil class, and following country borders. For crops, livestock, and forest products, spatially explicit Leontief production functions covering alternative production systems are parameterised using biophysical models like Environmental Policy Integrated Climate Model (EPIC) or Global Forest Model (G4M). GLOBIOM covers major greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) based on IPCC accounting guidelines. These include N₂O from application of synthetic fertiliser and manure to soils, N₂O from manure dropped on pastures, CH₄ from rice cultivation, N₂O and CH₄ from manure management, and CH₄ from enteric fermentation, and CO₂ emissions/removals from above- and below-ground biomass changes for other natural vegetation following conversion. CO₂ emissions/removals from afforestation, deforestation, wood production in managed forests are estimated by the geographically explicit (0.5x0.5 degree) model G4M that is connected to GLOBIOM based on the parameters derived from G4M (Kindermann et al., 2006).

Annex 1 – Figure 1. GLOBIOM

Keywords: *Land use, agriculture, forestry, climate change adaptation, climate change mitigation, food security, sustainable development, global economic model*

Model type: *Partial equilibrium model, recursive dynamic*

Ownership: IIASA-IBF

Code sharing and license: Non-free model license. Access to the model is granted upon request to collaborators.

More about the model under: <https://iiasa.github.io/GLOBIOM/>

Details

Details on model structure and approach

GLOBIOM focuses on few sectors of the economy, crops, livestock, and forestry. The agricultural and forestry sectors are linked within a single model and compete for limited land available. On the other hand, a general equilibrium model encompasses the entire economy, and equilibrium in all markets must hold simultaneously: on the factor market, the goods and services market, the capital account, the government account, and current account. The impacts on one sector can affect other sectors through input and factor prices. The implications of a Partial Equilibrium (PE) in GLOBIOM are the following: i) there is no feedback from the sectors represented in the model to the rest of the economy, ii) there is no currency constraint on imports, iii) there is no constraint on government spending, and iv) markets for labour and capital are not represented. However, a partial equilibrium model allows for a more detailed representation of the selected sectors – higher spatial and commodity resolution. PE models also usually operate with quantities while Computable general equilibrium (CGE) models use values allowing for a better representation of environmental and biophysical impacts.

The economic formulation problem in GLOBIOM is expressed as follows: the model optimises an objective function defined as the sum of producer and consumer surpluses associated with the sector represented, under a certain number of constraints. Producer surplus is determined by the difference between market prices, at regional level, and the supply curve integrating the cost of the different production factors (labour, land, capital) and purchased inputs. International transportation costs are also considered in the producer costs. On the consumer side, surplus is determined by the level of consumption on each market -- the lower the price, the higher the consumption -- as well as the consumer surplus. This is achieved by integrating the difference between the demand function of the good on its market and the market price level. Constraints in the model are related to various dimensions: technologies available, biophysical resources availability (land, water), capacity constraints, etc.

In this type of approach, the supply side can be very detailed, the model can be solved as a linear programming (LP) model, allowing a large quantity of data to be used for production characteristics. New technologies and transformation pathways can coexist for the different sectors or be latent technologies. This detailed representation on the production side however induces a trade-off on the demand side. Because of the linear optimisation structure, demand is represented through separated demand functions, without a representation of total households budget and the associated substitution effects.

As GLOBIOM is a partial equilibrium model, the relevant sectors (agriculture and forestry) are represented in detail, an important factor for representing land use change impacts of biofuel policies. Other economic sectors however are not included, or only represented through an external variable (e.g. price of fertiliser, price of fossil fuel). GLOBIOM assumes that the economy outside land use sectors evolves independently from the policies assessed in the model, following a ceteris paribus approach. The missing effects from the general equilibrium approach, when expected to drive first order impacts, can be added to the simulation of the model through linkages with other models.

The market equilibrium maximises the sum of consumer and producer surpluses under a set of constraints including the market balance constraint. These are discrete constraints that encompass equalities and inequalities. In linear programming, the feasible region is a closed convex set, i.e. to select the optimal solution we need to find the set of all extreme points instead of finding the entire feasible region. An important feature of linear programming is that any solution obtained provides both, a local and global optimum. GLOBIOM also contains some non-linear functions, but they have been linearised using stepwise approximation. The model is solved using the linear programming solver Cplex in GAMS. In this set-up, prices are not explicit but are given by the dual of the market balance equations.

GLOBIOM is run for several periods (at 10-year time steps) following some recursive dynamics. Contrary to fully dynamic models, the agents of the economy do not make strategic decision considering future value of some parameters over several periods of time. However, the optimal decision in time period t depends on some decisions that agents have taken in the previous time period $t-1$. For instance, in GLOBIOM, at the beginning of a time period, the starting conditions for land use are updated using the solutions of the simulations from the previous time period. Moreover, the reference is updated for each time step using exogenous drivers. For crops, livestock products and timber products, projections of population and GDP growth per region are used to set-up the initial demand level before market adjustments. Demand for bioenergy is set-up exogenously using outputs of energy models or policy targets.

Baseline scenario

Within the baseline scenario, GLOBIOM seeks to understand the business as usual (BAU) land management, which includes both practices and policies associated with them. The baseline scenario also assumes no changes in the production systems, or any climate mitigation efforts. The projections into the future take the reference RCP scenario and the SSP2 scenario. Using 2000 as a base year, GLOBIOM calculates the impacts of land use change on demand and supply quantities, trade flows, and other indicators at a 10-year time interval up to 2100. The importance of such a baseline is to have a reference point for comparison and assessment, and to implement policies and plans to achieve different climate goals. The GLOBIOM uses 2000 to 2020 projections to validate the data with historical trends. The baseline scenario, through the SSP2, helps us understand the impacts of population and GDP based on the SSP2 scenarios to assess the impacts of such growth on land use change, prices, demand, supply, and other indicators.

Input and parametrization

Please list the key inputs used for the model.

- National/regional market balances (harvested areas, yields, production, consumption, prices etc.) for model calibration (FAOSTAT)
- Spatially explicit productivities and input requirements for crops differentiated by management intensities (EPIC)
- Spatially explicit pasture productivities (CENTURY, EPIC)
- Spatially explicit forestry increments (G4M)
- Initial crop area distribution by management system (SPAM)
- Initial land cover map (GLC2000)
- Initial carbon stocks in above- and belowground biomass (G4M, Ruesch and Gibbs 2008)
- Population and GDP (various sources)
- Biofuel and bioenergy demands (various sources)

Main output

Typically, the model results are reported in the AgMIP or IAMC template which covers amongst other information on:

- Market balances and activity levels: production, areas, yields, food-, feed-, other consumption, bilateral trade flows etc.
- Socio-economic indicators: such as product prices, food consumption, undernourishment etc.
- Environmental indicators: land use and land use changes, deforestation, GHG emissions, fertiliser and irrigation water use, biodiversity impacts etc.

The output has the following spatial-temporal resolution and extent:

Parameter	Description
Spatial Extent / Country Coverage	Global
(Spatial) resolution	59 Regions
Temporal extent	2000-2100 at 10-year time steps
Temporal resolution	10 years

Relationships with other models

Model name	ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
The Environmental Policy Integrated Climate Model	EPIC	Crop-growth model providing biophysical input for the crop sector representation
Global Forestry Model	G4M	Forest-growth model providing biophysical input for the forestry representation
Ruminant Model	Ruminant	Livestock digestibility model providing biophysical inputs for the livestock sector representation

Quality and reliability

Criterion	Is the criterion met?	Details
Have uncertainties been quantified in the model runs?	Yes	Scenarios to test model uncertainty can be added to main analyses
Has the model undergone sensitivity analysis?	yes	Scenarios to test model sensitivity can be added to main analyses
Has the model undergone external peer review (by a panel of experts)?	Yes	Model results have been published in peer-reviewed journals
Has model validation been done? Model predictions have been confronted with observed data (ex-post analysis).	Yes	The model is validated using 2000-2020 data

Peer-review for model quality and reliability (panel review or peer-review in scientific journals):

- Not Provided

Transparency

Criterion	Meets criterion	Details
Is the model input data / underlying database (i.e. the database the model runs are based on) made publicly available?	No	
Can model outputs be made publicly available?	Yes	
Are model equations and data base transparently documented and are these documents available to the general public?	Yes	
Is the model source code publicly accessible?	No	

References related to documentation:

- E.g. GLOBIOM model documentation:
https://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/18996/1/GLOBIOM_Documentation.pdf

Policy relevance and intended role in the policy cycle

The model is designed to contribute to the following policy areas:

- Agriculture
- LULUCF
- Climate and Energy policies
- Food security
- Environment
- International Trade
- Regional Policy
- Sustainable Development

Use of GLOBIOM by clients

National:

EU: DG CLIMA, ENE, ENV, MOVE, JRC,

International organisations: OECD, IEA, World Bank, CGIAR,

CAPRI – Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact model

Summary

CAPRI (Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact Analysis) is a global agri-economic model used to assess ex-ante the impacts of agricultural, environmental, and trade policies on the agricultural sector. CAPRI provides results at a regional level and for economic and environmental variables. The model originates from the University of Bonn (UBO) and is nowadays managed by EuroCare Bonn GmbH (EC), the Thünen Institute (TC), and the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) with many contributors by network partners across European research institutions and universities.

CAPRI has a supply module covering the EU and some auxiliary European countries (regional programming models for about 280 European regions, detailed coverage of agricultural policies) embedded in a market module covering regions in the rest of the world. Thus, it has global coverage but ignores potential interactions with non-agricultural sectors, except for land use. The supply module covers 55 agricultural inputs produced in about 60 activities. The activities include inputs to crop and livestock production from other sectors and intermediate inputs such as feed and young farm animals. The model captures in detail the premiums paid under CAP, including NPK balances and a module with feeding activities covering the nutrient requirements of animals. The market module for marketable agricultural outputs is a spatial, non-stochastic global multi-commodity model for about 65 primary and processed agricultural products. About 80 world regions are modeled but aggregated to 44 trade regions that trade bilaterally, with the possibility of simultaneous import and export. It simulates supply, demand, and price changes in global markets considering international trade.

The CAPRI database is generated from two major sources: EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT. Due to the level of detail required by CAPRI, the original EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT values are subject to the balancing process and are used to calculate additional required coefficients. This results in some differences between the original statistical values and the values of the CAPRI database. Other important data sources for land use and land use change are UNFCCC (CRF), Corine, Lucas, and the Hilda+ data set.

Post-model analysis includes calculating different income indicators such as variable costs, revenues, gross margins, etc., for individual production activities and for regions, according to the methodology of the Economic Accounts for Agriculture (EAA). A welfare analysis at the Member State level, or globally, at the country or country block level, covers agricultural profits, tariff revenues, outlays for domestic supports, and the money metric measure to capture welfare effects on consumers. Outlays under the first pillar of the CAP are modeled in detail. Environmental indicators cover NPK balances, including nitrogen leaching, and carbon balances, including carbon sequestration, and output of climate and air pollution relevant gases and biodiversity indicators.

Keywords: *partial equilibrium model, environment, agriculture, CAP, impact analysis, climate change, greenhouse gas*

Model type: *Comparative statistic, global partial equilibrium (CGE), explicit representation of market- and supply module*

Ownership:

Multiple copyright: CAPRI builds on an *open network approach* with activities managed by EuroCare Bonn GmbH (EC), Thünen Institute (TI), and Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) with other contributing partners European Commissions- Joint Research Center (JRC), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), European Commission – Joint Research Center (JRC – IES), Ruralis Norway, Directorate-General Agriculture (DG-Agri), Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW), Swiss Federal Office for Agriculture and Agroscope.

Code sharing and license:

License type: (Find correct name).

Specific license:

Details: CAPRI requires GAMS software with CONOPT solver license. Further, CAPRI requires a recent JAVA version to enable the Graphical user interface (GUI)

More about the model under: <https://www.capri-model.org>

Details**Details on model structure and approach**

The Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact (CAPRI) model is a global partial equilibrium agricultural sector model focusing on the European Union. It has been designed for ex-ante impact assessment of agricultural, environmental, and trade policies. It has a supply module covering the EU and some auxiliary European countries (regional programming models for about 280 European regions, detailed coverage of agricultural policies), embedded in a market module also covering regions in the rest of the world (global market model representing bilateral trade between 44 trade regions). Thus, it has global coverage but ignores potential interactions with non-agricultural sectors, except for land use.

The databases exploit, wherever possible, well-documented, official, and harmonised data sources, especially data from EUROSTAT, FAOSTAT, OECD, and extractions from the Farm Accounting Data Network (FADN). Specific modules ensure that the data used in CAPRI are mutually compatible and complete in time and space. They cover about 65 agricultural primary and processed products for the EU, from farm type to global scale, including input and output coefficients.

The economic model builds on a *philosophy of structurally identical model templates* so that instances for products and regions are generated by populating the template with specific parameter sets. This approach ensures the comparability of results across products, activities, and regions. It also allows low-cost system maintenance and enables integration with larger modelling networks. At the same time, the approach opens the chance for complementary approaches at different levels, which may shed light on aspects not covered by CAPRI or help to learn about possible aggregation errors in CAPRI.

CAPRI is designed for scenario analysis. It is a comparative static model, which technically means that the market equilibrium simulated for a given point in time does not involve lags or leads of endogenous variables. If several points in time are simulated, these simulations may be performed in any order or parallel. Comparative static results are best interpreted as the long-run outcome of some scenario after all adjustments to the new equilibrium are completed. CAPRI simulations start from a so-called baseline, a special application of the model. The CAPRI baseline integrates projections from external sources, typically the Agricultural Outlook published annually by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG-AGRI) (e.g. European Commission 2023). The parameters describing the reactions in the sector are calibrated to the baseline scenario, making the model behave in accordance with the data and projections. The baseline mirrors the projected agricultural situation up to some point in time and usually assumes status quo policy assumptions (currently: CAP 2014-2020, update to reflect CAP Strategic Plans by MS is underway in 2024). In a simulated scenario, all conditions in the baseline are maintained – except for the changes to be analysed.

Annex 1 - Figure 2: General structure of the CAPRI model

CAPRI contains two modules, market and supply, which interact (see Figure 1).

The *supply module* consists of independent aggregate non-linear programming models representing activities of all farmers at regional or farm type level captured by the Economic Accounts for Agriculture (EAA). The models optimise regional agricultural income, given the prices for inputs and outputs, subsidy levels, and other policy measures. These models are a kind of hybrid approach, as they combine a Leontief technology for variable costs covering a low and high-yield variant with a non-linear cost function that captures the effects of labour and capital on farmers' decisions. The non-linear cost function allows for perfect calibration of the models and a smooth simulation response rooted in observed behaviour (see also Jansson and Heckeley 2011).

Around 55 agricultural inputs produced in about 60 activities are covered in the supply module. The activities include inputs to crop and livestock production from other sectors and intermediate inputs such as feed and young farm animals. The models capture in great detail the premiums paid under CAP, including NPK balances and a module with feeding activities covering the nutrient requirements of animals.

The main constraints outside the feed block are arable and grassland, treated as imperfect substitutes, and potential policy restrictions (set-aside obligations, milk and sugar quotas, environmental constraints). Prices are exogenous in the supply module and provided by the market module. Grass, silage, and manure are assumed to be non-tradable and receive internal prices based on their substitution value and opportunity costs. A land supply curve renders agriculture responsive to returns to land. Non-agricultural areas respond in line with a given total region area, giving rise to land transitions.

The market module ensures an equilibrium calculated by iterations between the supply and market modules.

The market module for marketable agricultural outputs is a *spatial, non-stochastic global multi-commodity* model for about 65 primary and processed agricultural products. About 80 world regions

are modelled but aggregated to about 40 trade regions that trade bilaterally, with the possibility of simultaneous import and export. It simulates supply, demand, and price changes in global markets considering international trade.

Agricultural supply is modelled simpler than in the supply module, with behavioural functions for supply and feed demand. These are supplemented with other functions for processing, biofuel use, and human consumption. These functions apply flexible, functional forms where calibration algorithms ensure full compliance with microeconomic theory, including curvature. The parameters are synthetic, i.e., largely taken from the literature and other modelling systems. Consumers and traders are represented by economic agents that follow neo-classical microeconomic theory regarding behaviour, which makes it possible to compute welfare effects. Based on the Armington assumptions, bi-lateral trade flows and attached prices are modelled (Armington 1969). Policy instruments cover (bilateral) tariffs, the Tariff Rate Quota (TRQ) mechanism, and, for the EU, intervention stocks and subsidised exports. This market module delivers prices used in the supply module and allows for market analysis at global, EU, and national scales.

The supply models are solved independently at fixed prices, so the link between the supply and market modules is based on an iterative procedure. After each iteration, during which the supply module works with fixed prices, the constant terms of the behavioural functions for supply and feed demand are calibrated to the results of the regional aggregate programming models aggregated to Member State level. Solving the market modules delivers new prices. A weighted average of the prices from past iterations then defines the prices used in the next iteration of the supply module. Equally, in between iterations, CAP premiums are re-calculated to ensure compliance with national ceilings, and crop yields may respond to changing market prices.

Environmental indicators, primarily for nutrient surpluses and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, are calculated in CAPRI and may be directly addressed in some scenarios. The supply module contains nutrient balance equations for nitrogen, phosphorous, and potassium regarding nutrient surpluses. It considers nutrient uptake by crops following a crop growth function, and supply of nutrients from mineral fertiliser, manure, crop residues, and, for nitrogen, atmospheric deposition and fixation. The balances also contain factors for over-fertilisation, loss rates, and nutrient availability per source. From those balances, nutrient surpluses can be calculated per region of the supply model. Technical information from the supply module is used to compute greenhouse gas emissions based on IPCC methodology. Globally, GHG emissions are computed based on estimated emission intensities per ton of product and production levels for globally traded commodities.

CAPRI allows for modular applications, e.g., regional supply models for a specific Member State may be run at fixed exogenous prices without any market module. In previous applications, farm heterogeneity has been represented by a set of farm types for each NUTS2 region, each with its own supply model. The farm-type model layer is currently being replaced with another solution that has been switched OFF in recent applications. Equally, the global market model can also be run in stand-alone mode.

Post-model analysis includes the calculation of different income indicators such as variable costs, revenues, gross margins, etc., both for individual production activities and for regions, according to the methodology of the EAA. A welfare analysis at the Member State level, or globally, at the country or country block level, covers agricultural profits, tariff revenues, outlays for domestic supports, and the money metric measure to capture welfare effects on consumers. Outlays under the first pillar of the CAP are modelled in great detail. Some of the post-model analysis options are designed to disentangle various contributions to scenarios. An important element of post-model analysis is the option of spatial down-scaling part to clusters of 1x1 km grid cells, covering crop shares, crop yields, animal stocking densities, fertiliser application rates, and derived environmental indicators. Model results are presented as *interactive maps* and as thematic *interactive drill-down tables*.

Baseline scenario

The CAPRI baseline relies on constrained trend projections based on the historical CAPRI database with time series starting in 1985 for many European countries. The keyword “constrained” points, on the one hand, to the integration of technical information (balancing equations, linkage of livestock herds to feed intake, etc). On the other hand, it also hints at the integration of projections from external sources. For the medium run, the most important source is typically the Agricultural Outlook, which is published annually by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG-AGRI) (European Commission 2023), running to 2040. For longer-run projections, CAPRI usually relies on projections by GLOBIOM, often prepared in the context of EUCLIMIT projects. In this context, energy-related items like new energy crop areas are usually aligned with the energy model PRIMES. For fertiliser projections, CAPRI integrates the projections by EFMA (which only cover the next 10 years). Depending on the context and purpose of the study or project, the weights for these sources may be adjusted to fit the CAPRI baseline into some larger framework.

In the process of the baseline preparation, the parameters describing the reactions in the sector are calibrated to the baseline situation, making the model behave in accordance with the data and projections. The baseline mirrors the projected agricultural situation up to some point in time and usually assumes status quo policy assumptions (currently: CAP 2014-2020, update to new CAP SPs is underway). In a simulated scenario, all conditions in the baseline are maintained – except for the changes to be analysed.

Input and parametrisation

Please list the key inputs used for the model.

- Activity levels – Hectares, slaughtered heads, or herd sizes (EUROSTAT/FAOSTAT database)
- Income indicators – Revenues, costs, gross value added, premiums (EUROSTAT database)
- Production quantities for activities (EUROSTAT/FAOSTAT database)
- Farm- and market balances – production, seed, and feed use, other internal use, losses, stock changes, exports/imports, human consumption, purchases, internal deliveries (EUROSTAT/FAOSTAT database)
- In- and output prices – Unit value prices from the Economic accounts for agriculture (EAA) with and without subsidies and taxes (EUROSTAT/FAOSTAT database)
- Consumer prices – (EUROSTAT Database)
- EAA positions – Value of outputs/inputs with or without subsidies and taxes linked to production/input use (EUROSTAT Database)
- Emission coefficients (IPCC, UNFCCC)
- GDP and population (various sources)
- Policy variables – mostly DG AGRI, sometimes international sources (MacMaps for tariffs)

Main output

- Economic indicators: production quantities, activity levels, feed and fodder consumptions, trade, income, CAP budget, and producer/consumer prices
- Environmental indicators: GHG emissions, NPK balances, energy use, water use, biodiversity

The output has the following spatial-temporal resolution and extent:

Parameter	Description
Spatial Extent / Country Coverage	Market module: Global Supply module: EU member states plus Turkey, Norway, and Western Balkan countries
(Spatial) resolution	Market module: EU member states, 44 non-EU trade blocks Supply module: NUTS2
Temporal extent	Base year 2017 or earlier (2020 is under construction), longest horizon so far was 2085
Temporal resolution	Comparative-static

Relationships with other models

CAPRI...	ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
can use output from	GLOBIOM	CAPRI uses the baseline key results on production, areas, and demand at the country level to further disaggregate this information in the CAPRI context to more items and regions. Under the SUPREMA project, it has been explored to use forest area and new energy crop area effects from GLOBIOM in CAPRI scenarios
	AGLINK-COSIMO	CAPRI uses the baseline key results on production, areas, demand, and prices at EU13/EU14/EU27 level to further disaggregate this information to the country level and below while often also disaggregating the items.
	MAGNET	Under the SUPREMA project, it has been explored to use input prices and GDP effects from MAGNET in CAPRI scenarios
can potentially be linked to	Farm scale models	CAPRI or other large-scale models may project prices to be used in farm-level modelling

Relationships with datasets

CAPRI	Related dataset	Origin	Details of the relationship
Requires as input	EUROSTAT data	European Commission	EUROSTAT provides data on agricultural production, economic key indicators, etc.
Requires as input	FAOSTAT data	FAO	
Requires as input	MacMap	Market Access Map	tariffs
Requires as input		DG-Agri	CAP, WTO commitments, FTAs, NTMs

Quality, reliability & transparency

Quality and reliability

Criterion	Is the criterion met?	Details
Have uncertainties been quantified in the model runs?	Partially	An infrastructure has been developed to handle yield uncertainty. Critical parameters or assumptions have been sometimes subject to a sensitivity analysis.
Has the model undergone sensitivity analysis?	yes	Scenario simulations are, in general, accompanied by sensitivity analyses
Has the model undergone external peer review (by a panel of experts)?	no	There has been no formal evaluation of the model by an external panel. However, the model has been

Criterion	Is the criterion met?	Details
		extensively published in peer-reviewed journals and is widely regarded as the state-of-the-art global partial equilibrium model of agricultural economics analysis.
Has model validation been done? Model predictions have been confronted with observed data (ex-post analysis).	Partially	For some reports, model predictions were contrasted with observed data. However, this is rather the exception than the rule.

Peer-review for model quality and reliability (panel review or peer-review in scientific journals):

- Not Provided

Transparency

Criterion	Meets criterion	Details
Is the model input data / underlying database (i.e. the database the model runs are based on) made publicly available?	Partly	EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT information are publicly available, but other sources are sometimes of a confidential nature (e.g. MacMaps). A full set of input data is freely downloadable for each of the StarX (stable release X) versions. The most recent database is only available to registered users, but registration is free of charge.
Can model outputs be made publicly available?	Yes	Through publications in reports and journals
Are model equations and databases transparently documented, and are these documents available to the general public?	Yes	CAPRI Online Manual: https://www.capri-model.org/dokuwiki_help/doku.php?id=start
Is the model source code publicly accessible?	Yes	A stable release is publicly available under: https://www.capri-model.org/dokuwiki_help/doku.php?id=getting_started_with_capri Current model developments are given out by agreement within the CAPRI Developer network.

References related to documentation:

- Documentation link: https://www.capri-model.org/dokuwiki_help/doku.php?id=start

Policy relevance and intended role in the policy cycle

The model is designed to contribute to the following policy areas:

- Agriculture
- Biobased economy
- Trade
- Economic and Monetary Affairs
- Energy
- Environment
- Climate policies
- Regional Policy

And the following phases of the policy cycle:

- Formulation – such as ex-ante Impact Assessments
- Anticipation – such as foresight and horizon scanning

Details

This economic simulation model, as a contribution to this impact assessment process, can provide insights into the effects of different policy scenarios on international trade and competitiveness.

The model is designed to conduct policy experiments, in which a reference scenario or baseline is first simulated over a future period and then, after changing one or more underlying assumptions (all kind of police instruments, tax, tariffs...), a new scenario incorporating these changes is run, also over the same time period. Comparison of the new scenario with the reference scenario at a given point in the simulation period, usually in terms of percentage differences, establishes the direction and relative magnitude of the impacts on all the endogenous variables of the change that is depicted in the hypothetical scenario at that point in time.

Use of CAPRI by clients

National administrations:

- Germany (linkage to Ministry of Agriculture via TI)
- Spain (studies supporting Spanish agencies via UPM)
- Sweden (Linkage via SLU)

Switzerland:

- Swiss federal office of Agriculture

EU:

- JRC – Seville and JRC – ISPRA
- Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development [DG-AGRI]
- Directorate-General for Climate Action [DG-CLIMA]
- Directorate-General for the Environment [DG-ENV]
- EEA, Copenhagen

International organizations:

- Occasional studies for OECD

NGOs:

- Various agencies (Swedish Energy board, COPA COCEGA Brussels, Agora Berlin, Nova Institut Hürth and others)

Private sector:

- Occasional studies for private companies (John Deere, BASF)

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AGMEMOD: Agricultural Member State Modelling

The AGMEMOD consortium currently involves the following active members from research institutes and universities in EU and non-EU countries:

- Croatia: University of Zagreb; Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences Osijek
- Denmark: University of Copenhagen, Department of Food and Resource Economics
- France: Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA)
- Germany: Thünen Institute
- Hungary: AKI - Research Institute of Agricultural Economics
- Ireland: Irish Agriculture and Food Development Authority (TEAGASC)
- Latvia: Latvia University of Agriculture (LLU)
- Netherlands: Wageningen Economic Research
- Poland: Warsaw university of Life Sciences
- Slovakia: Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra
- Slovenia: University of Ljubljana and Agricultural Institute of Slovenia
- Spain: European Commission, Joint Research Centre
- Ukraine: Kyiv School of Economics; Ivan Franko National University of Lviv
- Italy: CREA-PB
- Argentina: BCR
- China: Institute of agricultural economics and development ,Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences

Because of the dynamic nature of the AGMEMOD consortium, this list doesn't reflect all partners that have been involved in the creation and development of the model since 2021. For example, in the publication 'The Future of agricultural markets by AGMEMOD (Chantreuil et al, 2012), one can find the names of AGMEMOD members at the time when this was published.

Overview

The AGMEMOD model is used to provide medium term outlooks for agrifood and bio-based markets in EU member states under baseline and alternative policy scenarios.

Summary

AGMEMOD is an econometric, dynamic, partial-equilibrium, multi-country, multi-market model that covers the main EU agri-food markets at Member State (MS) level. AGMEMOD has an extensive track record supporting DG AGRI on the preparation of the medium-term outlook for the EU's agricultural markets. Here, in addition of providing insights at MS level for the standard AGLINK commodities, AGMEMOD can also make an important contribution in the case of specialised crops, i.e. various fruits and vegetables, which are not modelled in AGLINK. Apart from delivering baseline developments, AGMEMOD can be used for simulating scenarios up to 2035 (or 2050). Over time it has been extended to capture non-EU countries (Ukraine, Russia, Turkey, some Balkan countries) and a stylised version of the rest of the world.

The current version of the model includes: six types of cereals, three types of oilseeds and their processed products, oil and meal, sugar beet and sugar, protein crops and potatoes, live animals (cattle, pigs, sheep and goats) and meats (beef, pig meat, poultry, sheep and goat meat), raw milk and

its processed products drinking milk, cream, fresh dairy products, butter, skimmed milk powder, whole milk powder and cheese. Vegetables and fruit commodities are currently being further developed.

The development of the AGMEMOD model and partnership has been continuously supported by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC). Apart from support for the model's general development and updating, AGMEMOD has been used for analysis of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reform (see AGMEMOD Partnership, 2007; 2023), analysis of the European milk and dairy market (see AGMEMOD Consortium, 2009; Jongeneel, 2023), analysis of potential impacts of Turkish EU membership (see Salamon et al., 2010; Fellmann et al., 2012), UK's exit (Van Berkum et al., 2018) and the Russian invasion in Ukraine (Jongeneel et al., 2021). Further the model was used to conduct market outlook studies for Ukraine (see van Leeuwen et al., 2012; Nykolyuk et al., 2021) and Russia (see Salputra et al., 2013). The AGMEMOD model has also been applied and further developed in diverse EC Framework Programmes (e.g. Agricistrade, SUCCESS, BioMonitor, Tools4Cap). The results of these projects have provided the basis for numerous publications in scientific journals and conference proceedings (see Salamon et al., 2008; Erjavec et al., 2011; Salputra et al., 2011; Banse et al., 2012; Gonzalez-Martinez et al., 2021; Haß, 2021; Haß 2022; Jongeneel et al., 2022; Jongeneel et al., 2023).

Apart from its focus on agri-food markets, AGMEMOD has been extended with the BioMAT module that delivers baseline and scenario analysis for bio-based material markets in EU member states. In combination, AGMEMOD and BioMAT deliver improved insight in EU's produced biomass on the one hand and how it is distributed over food, feed, seed and material uses on the other hand (Sturm et al., 2023; Van Leeuwen et al., 2023).

Keywords: *CAP policy, EU member state model, multi-commodity model, baseline, agrifood commodity market, biobased commodity market, biomass competition*

Model type: *Recursive dynamic, econometrically estimated, partial equilibrium (PE)*

Ownership:

Multiple copyright: **AGMEMOD consortium**, led by Wageningen Economic Research and the Thünen-Institute. The consortium includes institutes from EU member states, non-EU countries (Serbia, BiH, Ukraine, Argentina, China) and the Institute for Prospective Technological Studies (IPTS) in Seville.

Code sharing and license:

AGMEMOD consortium members have signed a Memorandum of Understanding. They get free access to the entire modelling framework, and in principle responsible for data and model development, update and validation of the own country.

Details: AGMEMOD needs GAMS software and consortium partner have to buy their own licence

More about the model under: <https://www.agmemod.eu/>

Details

Details on AGMEMOD structure and approach

General characteristics: country and commodity scope

AGMEMOD is an econometric, dynamic, partial-equilibrium, multi-country, multi-market model that covers the main EU agri-food markets at Member State (MS) level. AGMEMOD has an extensive track record supporting DG AGRI on the preparation of the medium-term outlook for the EU's agricultural markets. Here, in addition of providing insights at MS level for the standard 'AGLINK' commodities (grains, oilseeds, livestock and dairy), AGMEMOD can also make an important contribution in the case of specialised crops, i.e. various fruits and vegetables, which are not modelled in AGLINK. Apart from delivering baseline developments, AGMEMOD can be used for simulating (policy) scenarios up to 2035

(or beyond). Over time it has been extended to capture non-EU countries (Ukraine, Russia, Turkey, some Balkan countries) and a stylised version of the rest of the world.

The current version of the model includes: six types of cereals, three types of oilseeds and their processed products, oil and meal, sugar beet and sugar, protein crops and potatoes, live animals (cattle, pigs, sheep and goats) and meats (beef, pig meat, poultry, sheep and goat meat), raw milk and its processed products drinking milk, cream, fresh dairy products, butter, skimmed milk powder, whole milk powder and cheese. The vegetables and fruit commodities that recently have been added to the framework are apples, tomatoes, olives and olive oil, peaches and nectarines, and oranges (in development).

Apart from its focus on agri-food markets, AGMEMOD has been extended with the BioMAT module that delivers baseline and scenario analysis for bio-based commodity markets at MS level. In combination, AGMEMOD and BioMAT deliver improved insight in EU produced biomass versus the competition over food, feed, seed and material uses.

Approach

AGMEMOD provides significant detail on the main agricultural sectors in each EU Member State. Generally, the system has been econometrically estimated at individual Member State level and produces results for the EU as a whole as for individual countries. In some cases, parameters have been calibrated, where estimation was not feasible or meaningful. The country models contain the behavioural responses of economic agents to changes in prices and in policy instruments and to other exogenous variables in the agricultural market. Commodity prices adjust so as to clear all commodity markets considered on the world market. Quantitative baseline projections are generated for a medium-term horizon on an annual basis. These econometrically estimated country-specific agricultural market models provide a sound basis for analysing the impacts of changes facing EU agri-food markets in the future. The models comprise equations for those commodities that represent the majority of the agricultural output in each country.

In the crop sector, first, land (e.g. arable land) is allocated across crops by a pure top-down approach, i.e. changes in various land categories on different levels affect the land available for crop production. The behavioural equations for land allocation are expressed as proportions of the higher level. For example, changes in forest area or other land determines the usable agricultural area, all expressed as a proportion of total land. Usable agricultural area is then further split into subcategories, until finally the producers choose the proportion allocated to the various crops, e.g. soft wheat. The most important explanatory variables are expected (moving average) gross margins of the categories or crops, as well as competing categories or crops at the same level. These expected gross margins include expected yields and expected prices, including a policy support component. Further explanatory variables in the land proportion equations can be trend variable, own-lagged proportions and others

Animal products cover projections on stocks of live animals, slaughter and trade in live animals. The key in all livestock models is to determine the ending numbers of breeding animals, considering among other things price and cost variables, such as coupled or decoupled payments, and specific national policy instruments. Also essential is the number of animals produced by breeding under consideration of the productivity. Ending stocks of each type of animals (breeding and non-breeding) are derived by capturing beginning stocks, animals produced, exports and imports of live animals, slaughtering and other losses (Chantreuil et al., 2012). Within each livestock group there is a category of animals to be slaughtered. Those animals and their simulated average slaughter weight allow meat production per category to be determined, while domestic use, per capita use, trade in meat and domestic prices are other main items projected for animal markets.

The dairy sub-model comprises two levels: on the first level, milk production, milk imports, exports, on-farm use and deliverables to dairies are determined, with the last of these closing the balance. Milk

production is defined by an equation considering prices, costs, an assumption on quota rents under the pre-quota abolition phase and assumptions on elasticities. In addition, milk yield per cow is determined by an equation capturing productivity by a trend and a price. As a consequence, dairy cow ending numbers are defined as an identity. At a second level, the AGMEMOD model allocates fat and protein to different dairy products based on assumptions or estimates concerning the fat and protein content of raw milk and other dairy commodities. Allocation of fat and protein depend on the prices of dairy commodities and other exogenous and endogenous variables (Chantreuil et al., 2012).

In principle, equations to determine endogenous variables describe the behavioural responses of economic agents (farmers, consumers, etc.) to changes in, for example, market prices, policy instruments and other exogenous variables, as well as in lagged endogenous variables. The lagged variables induce a recursive model structure. For each commodity, sets of behavioural equations describe the supply side (beginning stocks, production and imports) and demand sides (domestic use, exports and ending stocks) of the market. Supply and demand equations define how, in any given year, equilibrium (i.e. supply equals demand) is found within the single commodity market. Lagged endogenous variables introduce (recursive) dynamic behaviour when entered as determinants in the next period's equilibrium supply and/or demand (Chantreuil et al., 2012).

Different sectors are linked in supply and demand (see Figure 4). Detailed information on the general structure of the AGMEMOD country model equations can be found in Hanrahan (2001), Esposti and Camaioni (2007) and Chantreuil et al. (2012). To solve the modelling system in prices, the supply and utilisation balances of each product at both the EU and the Member State level must hold and take into account the international trade and other commitments of the EU, such as tariff rate quotas (TRQs). The AGMEMOD composite model requires equations that impose the market equilibrium or closure (supply equals demand) for any commodity at global level, which is achieved by the integration of a stylised ROW model, where international prices are formed by closing global balances. Various domestic commodity markets are linked to each other by substitution or complementary parameters on the supply or demand side. There is competition between the various crops to use the available land. Interactions between the crops and livestock sub-models are captured via the derived demand for feed. In addition to raw milk and dairy products, the dairy sector provides calves that are exported or raised as cattle to produce beef. The various meat types, dairy products and crops are partly substitutes in demand, while cattle, pig, sheep and goat, and poultry compete for feed.

Price formation

Prices in AGMEMOD are formed essentially in three ways: for most Member States and commodities, they are defined by a price transmission equation, whereas a domestic price in a given country is driven by an external price in the so-called key-price country or the ROW region. In principle, the national price of a commodity is explained by the key price of that commodity and a vector of exogenous variables, including the self-sufficiency rate (production divided by domestic use) in the relevant country and the self-sufficiency rate for the same commodity in the key-price market (Chantreuil et al., 2012). With a key-price country that normally corresponds to the most important market for that commodity (e.g. France for soft wheat), the price formation equation links the domestic market to the world market and captures all exogenous variables affecting price formation and the dynamic structure at the EU combined level. In particular, next to the world market price, price policies (e.g. intervention prices) and trade measures (e.g. TRQs) are included in the key-price equation, thus indirectly affecting all country prices via price transmission equations. In addition, key-price equations include as a determinant the EU self-sufficiency rate, thus making the key-price (and other linked prices) responsive to the EU supply and use balance of the commodity concerned (Chantreuil et al., 2012). In addition, the AGMEMOD model requires equations that impose market equilibrium or closure (supply equals demand) for any commodity at a global level, implying that production plus beginning stocks plus imports must always equal domestic use plus ending stocks plus exports. AGMEMOD commodity models, however, do not represent closed economies, so that the

ROW markets play a role in the domestic markets modelled. To achieve this objective, a regional module covers the ROW. As a result of data restrictions and the obvious extreme heterogeneity of the aggregate, it is established in a stylised way and does not capture any policy measures affecting consumption, production and trade. The ROW's production and consumption are driven directly by world prices, without driving any wedges between world and producer or consumer prices. Parameters of the behavioural supply and demand equations are not estimated econometrically but are derived from other models and literature. World market prices clear the commodity market on a global level, while the EU key markets are then linked to the ROW market. The total net trade of EU and the other represented markets affects the domestic use of commodities in the ROW and, thus, the EU affects the relevant world price formation. To deal with a changing number of countries included in the model, data cover the world total figures and the ROW is then calculated as the difference between world total and the countries included in the model.

Modelling platform

The AGMEMOD model is an integral part of the Integrated Modelling Platform for Agro- economic Commodity and Policy Analysis (iMAP) hosted by the JRC (M'barek et al., 2012; M'barek and Delincé, 2015). Together with CAPRI and AGLINK, AGMEMOD is one of the three core PE models in the platform. In the PE model family, AGMEMOD provides a unique advantage in combining other models' approaches in two ways. First, from a spatial point of view, it provides projections at the Member State level, establishing a bridge between AGLINK's aggregate projections and CAPRI's regional ones. Second, from a calibration perspective, AGMEMOD combines the information provided by AGLINK for the various EU aggregates, together with market intelligence gathered by the modelling teams in direct discussion with national market experts and at a specific validation workshop, organised by the EC together with the AGMEMOD consortium.

Baseline scenario

The AGMEMOD consortium develops its annual agri-food commodity outlook in close cooperation with the JRC and the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG-AGRI). The process to achieve the AGMEMOD outlook mimics that which leads to the EC's EU Agricultural Outlook as reported in December of each year. The starting point for the AGMEMOD Outlook process are aggregate projections for the 27 Member States of the EU (EU-27), the 14 countries that were Member States prior to the accession of 10 candidate countries in 2004 (EU-15), and the 13 Member States that acceded to the EU between 2004 and 2013 (EU-N13). AGMEMOD is updated first with the latest assumptions used for the EU Agricultural Outlook regarding the development of macroeconomic conditions (gross domestic product (GDP) growth, inflation, exchange rates, population growth). These data are complemented with Member State-specific macroeconomic data obtained from national sources in the Member States. The AGMEMOD Member State models are then updated with the latest EU policy assumptions regarding the CAP and its specific implementation at Member State level. As far as possible, national policies with a potential impact on the national agricultural sector beyond the CAP are also taken into account. An example of such an additional national policy is an environmental policy that constrains dairy, pig and poultry production. This is explicitly implemented in the models of the Netherlands (including the recent phosphate reduction measures), Germany and Denmark. Complementing the EU Agricultural Outlook medium-term projections, the latest EU agricultural short-term outlook (for the publication at hand this was DG AGRI, 2017) is taken into consideration when carrying out the first AGMEMOD baseline runs. The results of this first run are checked and when implausible figures are obtained the model is debugged and rerun, until a coherent draft of the AGMEMOD baseline projections for EU Member States is available. This draft baseline result is then discussed with internal AGMEMOD and external national agricultural market experts. The feedback obtained in these discussions is used to revise and adjust the Member State models. The next step in the validation process is the organisation of the AGMEMOD Outlook workshop by the AGMEMOD consortium, the JRC and DG AGRI. In the pre-covid period they were held in Brussels

around the end of February/beginning of March, and since 2021 it are online workshops with market experts. The aim of the workshop is to present and discuss the preliminary results of the agricultural outlook at EU Member State level. As far as possible, comments made during the workshop about expected market developments are then incorporated and final model adjustments are made, leading to the final AGMEMOD agri-food projections for EU Member States.

Input and parametrisation

Following list contains the key inputs used for the AGMEMOD model:

a) Data inputs for historical period and the entire projection period (e.g. until 2040):

- Population per country (million persons). Source: DG-AGR
- GDP per country (billion euro). Source: DG-AGR
- Real GDP at 2010 market prices per country (billion euro, in 2010 prices). Source: DG-AGR
- Real GDP at 2010 market prices per capita, per country (billion euro, in 2010 prices). Source: DG-AGR
- GDP deflator, base year 2010, per country (2010=1, euro). Source: DG-AGRI
- Exchange rate national currency/Euro per country (national currency/euro). Source: DG-AGRI
- Exchange rate Euro/USD (USD/euro). Source: DG-AGRI
- World prices per agrifood commodity (US\$/tonne for crops and dairy products; US\$/100 lb dw for meat products). Source: AGLINK projections
- World price for bio-based chemical products (US\$/tonne). Source: expert information nova-Institute (Germany)
- Trade measures per commodity for EU and per country, e.g. import tariffs, export support, bans (% , per tonne, per euro). Source: EU regulations; national reports
- CAP policy targets and instruments, per country (metrics depends on the measure: tonnes, head, euro/kg, euro/tonne, euro/head, percentages, rates). Source: EC regulations; National Strategic Plans; JRC master file with NSP targets and instruments
- Renewable Energy Directive (RED) biofuel targets, per country (1000 tonne). Source: EC regulations
- National policy targets and instruments, e.g. on animal rights, water directives, biodiversity (metrics depend on the measure). Source: national policy regulations; national experts
- GHG emission for crop and livestock commodities (N₂O, CH₄, Co₂eq), per country (1000 tonne CO₂eq). Source: UNFCCC; IPCC 202
- Protein content per crop and animal commodity, per country (% per kg consumed product). Source: RIVM (NL)
-

b. Data inputs for historical period:

- Market balance items, like production, food use, feed use, seed use, stocks, imports and exports; per commodity, per country (1000 tonne; 1000 head). Source: EUROSTAT, DG-AGRI, FAO
- Prices per commodity, per country (euro/tonne; euro/kg). Source: EUROSTAT, DG-AGRI, FAO, national statistics

- Protein and fat contents of dairy commodities, per country (1000 tonne; %). Source: EUROSTAT, dairy market experts

The use of AGMEMOD requires, at a minimum, an understanding of agrifood markets (driving factors, supply and demand behaviour, key performance indicators) and an ability to read GANS code.

Main output

Following list contains the key output indicators of the AGMEMOD model:

- Production volumes per commodity, per country (1000 tonne)
- Land use, per crop category, per country (1000 ha)
- Yields per hectare, per crop category, per country (tonne/ha)
- Stocks for dairy cows, beef cows, pigs, poultry, sheep and goat, per country (1000 head)
- Milk yield per cow, per country (kg per cow)
- Slaughtering weight per animal type, per country (kg/animal)
- Domestic use per crop and animal commodity, per country (1000 tonne)
- Biomass allocated to food, feed, seed and material uses, per commodity, per country (1000 tonne)
- Net-exports per commodity, per country (1000 tonne)
- Prices per commodity, per country (euro/kg)
- GJG emissions for livestock and animal commodity types, per country (1000 tonne CO₂eq)
- Plant and animal protein intake per person, per country (gram, per person, per day)
- % plant based and animal-based proteins in total protein intake (%)

AGMEMOD analyses the impacts of policy, macroeconomic and/or structural supply and demand shocks on agrifood markets at the EU MS level (and in some non-EU countries). The output of AGMEMOD covers medium term projections of production, domestic use (for food, feed, seed, materials) levels, net-trade (all in volumes), prices (euros/kg), protein intake by consumer (gram per day per person), greenhouse gas emissions of livestock commodities (tonnes CO₂eq).

The output has the following spatial-temporal resolution and extent:

Parameter	Description
Spatial Extent / Country Coverage	EU countries; non-EU countries (UK, Ukraine, Serbia, BiH, Turkey, Russia)
(Spatial) resolution	Country
Temporal extent	Historical period: start year 1973/1990/2000, depending on data availability); end year 2022 (or earlier, depending on data availability)
Temporal resolution	Annual

Relationships with other models

AGMEMOD..	ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
provides input to	AGLINK-COSIMO	On EU-27, EU-14 and EU-13 aggregates as sum of individual MS agrifood markets; for validating

AGMEMOD..	ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
		AGLINK's EU-27, EU-14 and EU-13 aggregates of agrifood markets
provides input to	MAGNET	Agricultural production and use development; for calibration supply and demand side indicators
Use output from	AGLINK-COSIMO	EU-13 and EU-14 aggregates to scale AGMEMOD bottom-up/member states results for production, domestic use and trade.
can use output from	IMAGE	Land use data. The IMAGE crop and land-use models supply information to AGMEMOD on land supply by region and changes in potential yields
can use output from	FARMDYN	Cost structures and input coefficients for farm types (e.g. organic versus conventional farming)
can use output from	MITERRA-Europe	To connect AGMEMOD's agri-food market indicators with MITERRA's environmental indicators (nitrate and other GHG emissions); MS based
can use output from	MAGNET	Ex ante development of world prices from MAGNET (endogenous) can guide world price projections in AGMEMOD (exogenous)
can be linked to	CAPRI	For calibration issues related to production and domestic use volumes
can be linked to	KOBALAMI (NL)	Provides cost-benefits e.g. of (new) investments in Dutch agro-complexes, based on IO coefficients
can be linked to	MAGNET	AGRICISTRATE (FP7 project) via agrifood production levels, land use, agricultural prices
can be linked to	MAGNET	BioMonitor (HORIZON) via biobased industry and agrifood production levels, land use, agricultural prices

Relationships with datasets

AGMEMOD..	Related dataset	Origin	Details of the relationship
requires as input	Market item data; prices; land use (historical annual data); per member state	EUROSTAT; DG-AGRI MTO; DG-AGRI dashboards	Aligning with DG-AGRI in respect to AGMEMOD's role in contributing to DG-AGRI annual EC agricultural outlook report
Requires as input	CAP policy data (historical and projected), per member state	National Strategic Plans; JRC Mater file; EC's directives	Annual update/aligning of policy data needed due to AGMEMOD's role in contributing to DG-AGRI annual EC agricultural outlook report
Requires as input	Development of population, GDP/capita, inflation rate (historical and projected), per member state	DG-AGRI	To align with DG-AGRI outlook development process
Requires as input	World market prices (historical and projected)	AGLINK, OECD	To align with DG-AGRI outlook development process

AGMEMOD..	Related dataset	Origin	Details of the relationship
Requires as input	Greenhouse gas emission per crop and animal (historical and projected)	UNFCCC; IPCC 202	To be related to AGMEMOD market volumes
creates as output	AGMEMOD country database on agrifood markets, including land and yields/ha and yields/animal; for projected period; per member state	EUROSTAT, DG-AGRI	Aligning with DG-AGRI in respect to AGMEMOD's role in contributing to DG-AGRI annual EC agricultural outlook report

Quality, reliability & transparency

Quality and reliability

Criterion	Is the criterion met?	Details
Have uncertainties been quantified in the model runs?	no	Not accounted for systematically, but most relevant ones tested via statistics and validation of outcomes by market experts
Has the model undergone sensitivity analysis?	yes	Scenarios to account mainly sensitivity are usually added to main analyses
Has the model undergone external peer review (by a panel of experts)?	no	There has been no formal evaluation of the model by an external panel, however the model has been extensively published in peer-reviewed journals and is regarded as state-of-the-art partial equilibrium model for agricultural and bioeconomy analysis.
Has model validation been done? Model predictions have been confronted with observed data (ex-post analysis).	yes	Baseline projections are regularly discussed and validated by market experts (EC, private industry), and may lead to finetuned assumptions (on driving factors) to meet better expected market trends. Scenario impacts (e.g. due to covid, Ukraine) are usually discussed with experts/stakeholders. In general, validation takes place on a project basis.

Peer-review for model quality and reliability (panel review or peer-review in scientific journals):

- Not Provided

Transparency

Criterion	Meets criterion	Details
Is the model input data / underlying database (i.e. the database the model runs are based on) made publicly available?	yes	After signing a MoU partners can get access to the entire database. Juridic and property rules are determined in the MoU.
Can model outputs be made publicly available?	yes	After signing a MoU partners get access to the entire database. Through publications in reports and journals, as well as in the data platform dataM.
Are model equations and data base transparently documented and are these documents available to the general public?	yes	See model documentation
Is the model source code publicly accessible?	Yes	After signing a MoU partners can get access to the entire database

Policy relevance and intended role in the policy cycle

The model is designed to contribute to the following policy areas:

- Agriculture
- Biobased economy
- Trade
- Food security
- Market economic affairs
- Environment
- Health and diets
- Climate policies
- Regional Policy

And the following phases of the policy cycle:

- Formulation
- Implementation
- Analysis
- Evaluation

Details

AGMEMOD makes simulations for agrifood markets in the EU as a whole and its member states, as well as for a set of non-EU countries (like UK, BiH, Serbia, Ukraine). Impacts of a specific simulations are calculated by comparing outcome indicators to a reference situation (baseline).

The model is designed to conduct policy experiments, in which a reference scenario or baseline is first simulated over a medium term future period and then, after changing one or more underlying assumptions (all kind of policy instruments, macroeconomic developments, supply and demand trends), a new scenario incorporating these changes is run, also over the same time period. Comparison of the new scenario with the reference scenario at a given point in the simulation period, usually in terms of percentage differences, establishes the direction and relative magnitude of the impacts on all the endogenous variables of the change that is depicted in the hypothetical scenario at that point in time.

Impact areas that AGMEMOD can help to assess

Impact types that can be assessed with the models include:

Impact area	Category	Subcategory	Can be assessed by AGMEMOD through
Economic	Markets	Supply shocks (technology, climate change, diseases), in a specific country/EU as a whole/rest of world	<i>Change in production, domestic use, trade and prices in EU countries</i>
Economic	Markets	Demand shocks (population, economic development), in a specific country/EU as a whole/rest of world	<i>Change in production, domestic use, trade and prices in EU countries</i>

Impact area	Category	Subcategory	Can be assessed by AGMEMOD through
Economic	Markets	World price shocks (agri-food commodities)	<i>Change in production, domestic use, trade and prices in EU countries due to changes on the world market</i>
Economic	Markets	National, EU and international policy shocks	<i>Change in production, domestic use, trade and prices in EU countries</i>
Economic	Net trade flows	Net export of EU	<i>Impacts on net-export position of EU versus rest of world</i>
Economic	Competition	Allocation of biomass over food, feed, seed and material uses. Market share & advantages in international context	<i>Market share by commodity by exports in each importing country</i>
Economic	Macroeconomic environment	Change in economic growth, migration patterns	<i>Impacts on self-sufficiency of agrifood commodities in EU</i>
Economic	Consumers and households	Consumer's ability to benefit from the internal market and to have access to food	<i>Impact on prices of domestic agrifood commodities; food security</i>
Environmental	Climate	Emission of greenhouse gases	<i>Changes in emission of crop and animal sector</i>
Environmental	Land use	Change in land use	<i>Land use in the EU</i>
Social	Health	Transition to healthy diets	<i>Impact on plant versus animal protein intake by person</i>

Connection to existing indicator classification schemes: (e.g. SDGs, SJOS, ...)

Description & notes	Indicator scheme
Agrifood commodity prices (affordable prices, access to food)	SDG1
Food consumption per capita	SDG1
Self-sufficiency rate per agrifood commodity (food availability)	SDG1
Plant and Animal protein intake per day per person	SDG1
Quantity of domestic primary agricultural production	SDG2
Domestic primary agricultural production	SDG2
Index of quantity of domestic primary agricultural production	SDG2
Quantity of agrifood imports by region	SDG2
Average agrifood imports by region quantity	SDG2
Food import quantity index	SDG2
Quantity of food exports by region	SDG2
Average food exports by region quantity	SDG2
Food export quantity index	SDG2
Average food price by region	SDG2

Food price index	SDG2
Value of consumption updated with quantities	SDG2
Total value of food consumption updated with quantities	SDG2
Average food consumption by region	SDG2
Food consumption quantity index	SDG2
Population	SDG2
Average food consumption per capita by region	SDG2
Food consumption quantity per capita index	SDG2
Gram plant-based protein intake per capita per day	SDG2
Gram animal-based protein intake per capita per day	SDG2
GDP per capita (in euros 2010 prices) in EU countries	SDG5
Crude vegetable oil used for biobased material and biofuels	SDG7
shares of biofuels use in total biobased material use	SDG7
Land demand for biomass use for biofuels, EU	SDG7
Land demand for biomass use for material, EU	SDG7
Greenhouse gas emissions per crop and animal type	SDG9
Regional GDP per capita	SDG10
GDP per capita (in euros 2010 prices) in EU countries	SDG10
Eurostat EU populations (in thousands of persons)	SDG10
Eurostat GDP (in millions euros 2014 market prices)	SDG10
Eurostat EU GDP (in millions euros 2014 market prices)	SDG10
Eurostat EU population (in thousands of persons)	SDG10

Use of AGMEMOD by clients

NL:

- Ministry of LNV
- Industries (dairy processing; feed)

EU:

- National ministries
- It is currently actively in use or followed by the following policy DGs:
 - Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development [AGRI]
 - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation [RTD]

International organisations:

- OECD

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FARMDYN

Overview

Summary

FarmDyn is a modular mixed integer bio-economic model that can simulate optimal farm management and investment decisions under different market, technological or policy conditions for a variety of farm types at single farm level. It was originally developed by the Institute of Food and Resource Economics (ILR) of the University of Bonn and accommodates both comparative-static and fully dynamic capabilities. The dynamic mode can be extended to include stochastic elements and different risk profiles. The modularity of FarmDyn allows it to, for example, adapt different fertilisation and manure regulations and practices, and add new farm branches. It was originally developed for German farming systems and includes a detailed database specific to Germany by default. This includes field operations, crop calendars, engineering specifications, yields, prices, costs and machinery. For dairy and cattle farming, FarmDyn considers processes such as raising and fattening, grazing patterns, weight gains, calving and lactation periods for dairy cows, cross-breeding, and sexing options. It also incorporates various grassland management practices, manure management, and related storage and application processes.

Investments in machinery, stables, and other farm structures are represented as integer variables, with the model accounting for on-farm labour requirements for different operations and maintenance tasks. Different-sized investments and labour-capital intensities are endogenously depicted, resulting in increasing returns-to-scale in branch sizes.

FarmDyn, initially developed through research projects, is currently maintained and enhanced by the Institute of Food and Resource Economics (ILR) at Bonn University and utilised by international partners. It undergoes quality management measures including automated testing and revision control system hosting. Recent improvements have focused on enhancing its applicability to regions beyond Germany, such as the Netherlands and other EU countries, by leveraging FADN data and improving code-data separation.

Ownership: Institute of Food and Resource Economics (ILR), University of Bonn

Code sharing and license:

More about the model under: <https://www.ilr1.uni-bonn.de/en/research/research-groups/economic-modeling-of-agricultural-systems/farmdyn>

Details

Details on model structure and approach

The bioeconomic model FarmDyn simulates the economic activity of a farm by maximizing the overall net present value under several constraints (such as farm endowment, policies, etc.) using Mixed-Integer Programming (MIP). Whereas the model already includes customisable parameters in order to simulate a hypothetical farm, we use real world data in the form of FADN to construct average farms in the EU. The model contains different modules that can be switched on or off depending on what is being modelled, such as, for example, the farm branch (dairy, cattle, pig, arable crop farming). Annex 1- Figure 3 shows a graphical representation of the modules and the interactions between them.

FarmDyn uses a template model employing a declarative approach to analyse the system, representing generic physical and financial relations based on decision variables, exogenous parameters, and equations. It provides a structured framework where essential structural components, shared across farm instances, are clearly delineated from the specific attributes unique

to each farm. These attributes may include details such as the existing livestock, genetic potential, available labour, ages of stable facilities and machinery, land ownership, and equity. Additionally, it accounts for the farm's market environment, encompassing input and output prices, yield potentials, household expenditures, and the willingness of the farmer and their family members to engage in off-farm work (Britz et al. 2014).

Annex 1 - Figure 3: FarmDyn modules. As seen in the FarmDyn homepage (Institute for Food and Resource Economics University of Bonn, n.d.)

Livestock farming

The herd module in FarmDyn tracks different types of cattle (like dairy cows, mother cows, calves, heifers, and bulls) on the farm each year. Heifers, starting as female calves, can be raised for different lengths of time (12, 21, 27 months), leading to first calving at ages 12, 33, or 40 months. Newborn calves can be sold right away, kept for a year, or raised into heifers or young bulls. The module considers factors like age, gender, breed, production goals, and genetic potential for milk yield in females. A simpler module for pigs is also available in FarmDyn. Unlike for dairy cows, it is assumed that sows leaving the herd are replaced by young sows bought from the market. The farm can sell piglets or use them for fattening. The feeding module ensures animals' needs are met, connecting them to the crops grown and purchases of feed.

Cropping module

The cropping activities in FarmDyn are detailed, with different crops, soil types, management intensities, and tillage options. Management intensities affect yields and nutrient needs, with corresponding adjustments in costs and labour requirements. Land is categorised as arable or permanent grassland, with land use decisions made yearly based on labour, machinery, and other restrictions. Labour needs are split into general farm management, branch-specific activities (like arable cropping or dairy), and specific farm operations, all dependent on farm size.

Machinery and equipment

FarmDyn also considers the aging and depreciation of farm structures and machinery. Stables, buildings, and machinery have fixed lifespans or operating hour limits before they need replacement. Investments in these are handled as binary choices, with options to restrict reinvestment to specific years to manage complexity. This approach allows for long-term planning while considering factors like labour availability and machinery lifespan. However, it is also possible to include continuous values

in relation to machinery and equipment investment decision (e.g. instead of an integer value, a tractor can be bought as a fraction). This depends on the research question and assumptions.

Fertilisation

FarmDyn implements different application methods for manure nitrogen (N): road spreading, drag hose spreading, and injection. These methods have varying costs, labour requirements, and effects on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Parameters for these methods, along with those for synthetic fertilisers, are defined in the "fertilizing" sub-module. Investment costs for additional machinery, like manure barrels and distribution consoles, are based on KTBL 2010 (pp.92-93). The lifetimes of the manure application components are defined by their capacity, such as a 12m³ vacuum tank wagon (lifetime transportation capacity of 120,000m³), a 15m drag hose spreader, and a 6m injector system. This allows FarmDyn to simulate the use of different manure application techniques, considering their costs, labour requirements, and environmental impacts, to help optimise farm management decisions.

Baseline scenario

Input and parametrisation

Current farm specific data (from FADN):

- Milk yield
- Livestock units
- Arable land area
- Grassland area
- Crop yields
- Annual working units
- Farm branch
- Observed rotational shares (used as the maximum rotational share in FarmDyn)

Current default data (KTBL handbooks, publications and other literature):

- Data on machinery and equipment (including type, price, depreciation)
- Silos (manure silo type, capacity, costs)
- Stables (capacity, prices, marginal labour requirement compared to most efficient stable)
- Feeds and nutrient contents of feed
- Field operations, related labour requirements, inputs like diesel, fixed & variable costs, operations per crop by tillage type
- Other variable costs of crops
- Variable costs for dairy cows, factors for stocking rate, labour requirement per animal per year, tractor hours per animal
- Emission factors

Main output

The main output in FarmDyn consists of results based on the optimisation of the farm income and can be presented in relative (t/ha, per head of animal, etc.) or absolute (at farm level) scale:

- Monetary:
 - Farm income

- Sales revenue
- Input requirement
- Variable costs
- Fixed costs
- Total variable costs
- Total allocable fixed cost
- Gross margins
- Marginals for land use
- Physical and environmental:
 - Emissions (N₂O, NH₃, NO_x, NO₃, CO₂, N₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) and their sources (enteric fermentation, fertiliser application, etc.)
 - Environmental impact (GWP)
 - Input use (pesticides, machinery, fertiliser (manure and mineral, intensity, decomposition into nutrients), feed, labour)
 - Nutrient balance (N and P)
 - Cropping plan

The output has the following spatial-temporal resolution and extent:

Parameter	Description
Spatial Extent / Country Coverage	European Union, Switzerland, Norway
(Spatial) resolution	Field, farm-level
Temporal extent	1 year (comparative static) to many (dynamic)
Temporal resolution	Month, Year

Relationships with other models

Model name	ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool	MAGNET	Updated prices
Common Agricultural Policy Regional Impact Analysis	CAPRI	Updated prices, NUTS2 manure and mineral fertiliser use, grassland yields
Global Biosphere Management Model	GLOBIOM	Commodity classification mapped, cost structure of mitigation technologies

Relationships with datasets

FarmDyn	Related dataset	Origin	Details of the relationship
Agronomic and technical data	KTBL handbooks	Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft e.V.	Main database used in FarmDyn for technology representation

		(KTBL)/ German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL)	
Farm endowments, output coefficients	FADN	DG AGRI	Aggregation of individual farm data to typical farms; endowments, activity levels, animal and land productivity

Quality, reliability & transparency

Quality and reliability

Criterion	Is the criterion met?	Details
Have uncertainties been quantified in the model runs?	No	No explicit systematic uncertainty analysis has been done
Has the model undergone sensitivity analysis?	Partly	Can be done using the GUI by specifying parameter ranges, for which the model executes a large number of combinations using probabilistic sampling. Not often done due to being impractical when checking with domain knowledge from experts.
Has the model undergone external peer review (by a panel of experts)?	NA	NA
Has model validation been done? Model predictions have been confronted with observed data (ex-post analysis).	Partly	Model results are published in peer-reviewed journals

Peer-review for model quality and reliability (panel review or peer-review in scientific journals):

- Not Provided

Transparency

Criterion	Meets criterion	Details
Is the model input data / underlying database (i.e. the database the model runs are based on) made publicly available?	Partly	Input data such as FADN data is not publicly available (other than aggregated standard results), but KTBL data and data from publications or literature is.
Can model outputs be made publicly available?	Yes	They can be made publicly available if sufficiently aggregated
Are model equations and data base transparently documented and are these documents available to the general public?	No	Model documentation is publicly available, but the equations and data are only in parts documented I datasets are from KTBL or literature then they are available.
Is the model source code publicly accessible?	Yes	Access to the source code can be requested from the ILR at Bonn University.

References related to documentation:

Britz, W., B. Lengers, T. Kuhn, and D. Schäfer. "A highly detailed template model for dynamic optimization of farms." *Institute for Food and Resource Economics, University of Bonn. Model Documentation* (2014). Institute for Food and Resource Economics University of Bonn. n.d. "FARMDYN a Dynamic Mixed Integer Bio-economic

Farm Scale Model.” Universität Bonn. <https://www.ilr1.uni-bonn.de/en/research/research-groups/economic-modeling-of-agricultural-systems/farmdyn>.

Policy relevance and intended role in the policy cycle

The model is designed to contribute to the following policy areas:

- Agriculture
- Biobased economy
- Trade
- Food security
- Circular economy
- Economic and Monetary Affairs
- Energy
- Environment
- Climate policies
- Regional Policy

And the following phases of the policy cycle:

- Formulation

Details

This economic simulation model, as a contribution to this impact assessment process, can provide insights into the effects of different policy scenarios on international trade and competitiveness.

The model is designed to conduct policy experiments, in which a reference scenario or baseline is first simulated over a future period and then, after changing one or more underlying assumptions (all kind of police instruments, tax, tariffs...), a new scenario incorporating these changes is run, also over the same time period. Comparison of the new scenario with the reference scenario at a given point in the simulation period, usually in terms of percentage differences, establishes the direction and relative magnitude of the impacts on all the endogenous variables of the change that is depicted in the hypothetical scenario at that point in time.

Impact areas that the model can help to assess

Impact types that can be assessed with the models include:

Impact area	Category	Subcategory	Can be assessed by MAGNET through

Connection to existing indicator classification schemes: (e.g. SDGs, SJOS, ...)

Description	Indicator scheme
	e.g. SG1

IMAGE

Overview

IMAGE is an ecological-environmental model framework that simulates the environmental consequences of human activities worldwide. It represents interactions between society, the biosphere and the climate system to assess sustainability issues such as climate change, biodiversity and human well-being. The objective of the IMAGE model is to explore the long-term dynamics and impacts of global changes that result from interacting socio-economic and environmental factors.

Summary

IMAGE is an integrated assessment modelling framework that simulates global and regional environmental consequences of changes in human activities. Detailed model documentation is available online (www.pbl.nl/IMAGE). The model has been designed to analyse large-scale and long-term interactions between human development and the natural environment and identify response strategies to global environmental change based on assessing options for mitigation and adaptation. The IMAGE framework is structured around the causal chain of key global sustainability issues and comprises two main systems: 1) the human or socio-economic system that describes the long-term development of human activities relevant for sustainable development; and 2) the earth system that describes changes in natural systems, such as the carbon and hydrological cycle and climate. The two systems are linked through emissions, land use, climate feedbacks and potential human policy responses. Most of the socio-economic parameters are simulated for 26 regions and most environmental parameters are calculated at a geographical grid of 30 by 30 min or 5 by 5 min.

Important inputs to the model are descriptions of the future development of direct and indirect drivers of global environmental change: exogenous assumptions on population, economic development, lifestyle, policies and technology change form a key input into the energy system model (TIMER) and the food and agriculture system model (MAGNET). TIMER is a system-dynamics energy system simulation model describing key trends in energy use and supply; changes in model variables are calculated based on information from the previous time step. MAGNET is a computable general equilibrium (CGE) model with high detail for the agricultural sector. It uses information from IMAGE on land availability, suitability, and changes in crop yields due to climate change and agricultural expansion into heterogeneous land areas. Together with the drivers described above, regional consumption, production and trade in agricultural commodities are computed. The results from MAGNET on production and endogenous yield changes are used in IMAGE to calculate spatially explicit land-use change and the environmental impacts on carbon, nutrient and water cycles, biodiversity, and climate. The Global Nutrient Model (IMAGE-GNM) is a process-based simulation model that calculates the fate of nitrogen⁴⁵ and phosphorus from land to sea^{46,47}. It is coupled with the hydrological model PCRGLOBWB, which provides all water fluxes. IMAGE-GNM describes the flow and retention/removal of N and P delivery from agricultural and natural soils to surface waters and the in-stream loss processes in all surface waters (lakes, reservoirs and rivers).

In IMAGE, the main interaction with the earth system is by changes in energy, food and biofuel production that induce land-use changes and emissions of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases. A key component of the earth system is the LPJmL model that is hard-coupled to IMAGE. LPJmL covers the terrestrial carbon cycle and vegetation dynamics. Based on the regional production levels and the output of LPJmL, a set of allocation rules in IMAGE determine the actual land cover. Climatic change is calculated as global mean temperature change using a slightly adapted version of the MAGICC 6.0 climate model⁴⁸. The changes in temperature and precipitation in each grid cell are derived from the

global mean temperature using a pattern-scaling approach. The model accounts for several feedback mechanisms between climate change and dynamics in the energy, land and vegetation systems.

Ownership: Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL)

Code sharing and license: Non-free model license. Access to the model is granted upon request to collaborators.

More about the model under: www.pbl.nl/IMAGE

Details

Details on model structure and approach

IMAGE comprises various sub-models describing the energy system, land use, agricultural economy, natural vegetation, hydrology, and the climate system. The models dealing with land use and food aspects are most relevant in the context of BrightSpace, and are described in more detail here.

The IMAGE sub-models representing the land use and food system are a suite of four models: Agriculture, forestry, land-use dynamics, and livestock systems. Demand for crop and livestock products, trends in agricultural intensification, and trade dynamics are provided by the economic general equilibrium model MAGNET (see MAGNET model fact sheet). The IMAGE-Land Management model also determines the area and location of irrigated and rainfed cropland on a 5-arc-minute geographical grid required to fulfil the demand for production of 16 crop categories (wheat, rice, maize, tropical cereals, other temperate cereals, pulses, soybeans, temperate oil crops, tropical oil crops, temperate roots & tubers, tropical roots & tubers, sugar crops, oil palm, vegetables & fruits, other non-food, luxury crops, spices, plant-based fibres). The historical locations and cropland and grazing land areas are based on the HYDE database (Klein Goldewijk et al., 2017). The expansion of agricultural land use follows empirically based statistical suitability layers derived from ESA-CCI land-use change data (Cengic et al., 2020). Livestock production is represented by five categories (beef, dairy, pigs, poultry, sheep and goats) in intensive and extensive systems considering variations between the 26 IMAGE regions in feed composition, feed efficiency, genetic animal productivity and age at slaughter (Bouwman et al., 2005; Lassaletta et al., 2019). The livestock production module determines the amount of feed crops and grass required to fulfil the demand for livestock production as calculated by MAGNET. Expansion or abandonment of grazing land depends on the demand for grass and follows the same allocation procedure as cropland. Restrictions to agricultural land conversion are implemented at the grid level to represent protected areas (Kok et al., 2023) and peatlands (Doelman et al., 2023). Timber production is modelled for four forest management systems: clear-cut, selective-cut (conventional or reduced impact logging) and wood plantations (Arets et al., 2011). Afforestation commitments from the NDCs are implemented in Brazil, India, China, and Indonesia. In addition, biodiversity impacts are calculated through the mean species abundance index based on the GLOBIO model (Schipper et al., 2020) and the biodiversity intactness index (Leclère et al., 2020).

The dynamic global vegetation model LPJmL (Müller et al., 2016) is incorporated to IMAGE to simulate crop yields, grassland productivity, vegetation dynamics, and the carbon and water cycles on a 30 arc-minutes geographic grid. LPJmL is based on multiple plant functional types (PFTs) categorised according to biophysical characteristics. Both natural and crop PFTs are represented. LPJmL also includes a full hydrological model with a river routing module that calculates river discharge, with lakes and reservoirs as additional water stores. It accounts for both "blue" water (water from rivers, lakes, aquifers, and dams) and "green" water (precipitation used by plants directly). The model also accounts for grid-explicit dynamic climate change impacts on agriculture, precipitation patterns, and temperature, affecting crop yields, water availability, crop water use efficiency, forest growth, deforestation emissions, and carbon stock (Jägermeyr et al., 2021; Schaphoff et al., 2018). Environmental Flow Requirements (EFR) are implemented to restrict water withdrawal in regions prone to water scarcity.

The IMAGE Global Nutrient Model (IMAGE-GNM) provides a spatial-explicit representation of the nitrogen and phosphorus balance and their effect on estimates of water quality (Beusen et al., 2015). For nitrogen, discussed in this study, the model accounts for incoming flows from synthetic fertiliser, animal manure, N fixation, and N deposition, and outgoing flows such as uptake by vegetation, leaching, denitrification, erosion, and ammonia volatilisation. The nutrient balance is combined with hydrological data and other nutrient sources (for example, wastewater from humans and industry, emissions from aquaculture) to calculate water quality in terms of N concentrations. An important policy measure that can be implemented is improved fertiliser efficiency, which reduces the amount of excess nitrogen implemented on the land, resulting in better water quality and lower N₂O emissions. Future N inputs are determined by the N use efficiency (NUE, $NUE = N \text{ removal} / \text{total N input}$). N yields are calculated from the scenario-specific crop production expressed in N using N contents for each of the 160 crops reported by FAO (Lassaletta et al., 2014). For a given NUE, total inputs can be calculated as $N \text{ yield} / NUE$. Fertiliser use is the difference between total N inputs, manure, biological N fixation and deposition. Biological N fixation is from the production of leguminous crops, according to Salvagiotti et al. (2008). Atmospheric deposition and livestock's manure production and attribution to cropland and grassland are calculated internally by the IMAGE-Land Management module.

Baseline scenario

For all scenario studies, the IMAGE model first elaborated “baseline” scenarios to understand development in the absence of deliberate policy interventions. Often, the baseline is a “business as usual” (BAU) scenarios, in which no changes in demand and production trends are assumed, and where also population and GDP development follow best-estimate estimation of historic trends. In the context of the SSP scenarios, uncertainty in future development is reflected by the definition of alternative baselines (SSP1, SSP3, SSP4, SSP5), next to the “business as usual” SSP2 (Ref Popp et al. 2016).

Input and parametrisation

Main data sources for the IMAGE model. For more detail, see also the documentation for all IMAGE submodules at https://models.pbl.nl/image/index.php/Welcome_to_IMAGE_3.2_Documentation

- Energy:
 - International Energy Agency (IEA);
 - various sources on technology assumptions
- Land use and agricultural production/consumption:
 - Data on national crop and livestock production, agricultural yields, and land resources from FAO
 - Historic land cover from HYDE (Klein-Goldewijk et al. 2017)
- Emissions:
 - EDGAR database, FAO emissions database
- Climate data (Historic climate data):
 - CRU global climate dataset;
 - AR45 data repository
- Costs data climate policy (other than energy)
 - Harmsen et al. 2019

Main output

The output has the following spatial-temporal resolution and extent:

Parameter	Description
Spatial Extent / Country Coverage	Spatial extent is global, covering 26 world regions
(Spatial) resolution	Spatial resolution is regional, and for the land-use and biophysical processes a 5 minutes and 30 minutes gridded resolution is available.
Temporal extent	Historic (1970) to current 2020, and for the scenario period until 2050 or 2100, depending on the project.
Temporal resolution	Annual or 5-yearly timesteps

All output is described in a visual way in this model diagram: <https://models.pbl.nl/image/images/5/54/BigFlowchart.png>

and for all single modules in the respective chapter of the IMAGE model documentation.

Relationships with other models

ACRONYM of related model	Details of the relationship
IMAGE	MAGNET
	Info from IMAGE to MAGNET: Land supply, climate effect on crop yield, baseline trends of crop and livestock intensification, costs of mitigation, afforestation, REDD. Info from MAGNET to IMAGE: regional production, demand and trade for agricultural commodities, intensification of livestock and crops.

Quality, reliability & transparency

Quality and reliability

Criterion	Is the criterion met?	Details
Have uncertainties been quantified?	yes	Participation in multi-model comparisons address model uncertainties
Has the model undergone sensitivity analysis?	yes	Scenarios to test model sensitivity are regularly part of scientific publications
Has the model undergone external peer review (by a panel of experts)?	yes	Model results are published in peer-reviewed journals, and IMAGE is evaluated by an advisory board every 6 years
Has model validation been done? Model predictions have been confronted with observed data (ex-post analysis).	Yes	The model is validated using 2000-2020 data

Peer-review for model quality and reliability (panel review or peer-review in scientific journals):

- IMAGE advisory board: <<add Red>>
- IMAGE publications: <https://www.pbl.nl/en/image/publications>

Transparency

Criterion	Meets criterion	Details
Is the model input data / underlying database (i.e. the database the model runs are based on) made publicly available?	yes	IMAGE builds on various databases, which are publicly available (see description of input data above).

Can model outputs be made publicly available?	yes	Model outputs available for various projects, and can also be made available for BrightSpace scenarios
Are model equations and data base transparently documented and are these documents available to the general public?	yes	Extensive model documentation on pbl.nl/image , and in numerous scientific papers
Is the model source code publicly accessible?	No	Open-access is under development

References related to documentation: models.pbl.nl/image/

Policy relevance and intended role in the policy cycle

The model is designed to contribute to the following policy areas:

- Agriculture
- Biobased economy
- Food security
- Circular economy
- Energy
- Environment
- Climate policies
- Nutrient cycles
- Biodiversity
-

And the following phases of the policy cycle:

- Formulation
- Evaluation (e.g. UNEP GAP report)

Use of (results from) IMAGE by clients

National:

EU: DG CLIMA

International organisations: UNEP, OECD, UNCCD, UNCBD

ANNEX 2: COMPARISON OF CHANGE INDICES BETWEEN MODELS

Annex 2 – Figure 1: Drivers of global demand – Change in total population in CAPRI/GLOBIOM/MAGNET from 2020 to 2050 for World and EUR aggregate and single EU countries

Annex 2 – Figure 2: Drivers of global demand – Change in total GDP in CAPRI/GLOBIOM/MAGNET from 2020 to 2050 for World and EUR aggregate and single EU countries

Annex 2 – Figure 3: Change in land use in CAPRI/GLOBIOM/MAGNET from 2020 to 2050 for World and EUR aggregate and single EU countries

Annex 2 – Figure 4: Change in crop production in CAPRI/GLOBIOM/MAGNET from 2020 to 2050 for World and EUR aggregate and single EU countries

Annex 2 – Figure 5: Change in yield in CAPRI/GLOBIOM/MAGNET from 2020 to 2050 for World and EUR aggregate and single EU countries.

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www.brightspace-project.eu
www.brightspace-horizon.eu

